

REWIRE:

A Generative Data-Driven Spatial
Construction Algorithm.

Third Year Project

INTERMEDIATE 5

with Ryan Dillon and David Green

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ABOUT REWIRE

REWIRE transcends traditional boundaries, merging **architecture, data, and political activism** in a unique protest against capitalistic banks while empowering day traders. At its core, REWIRE deploys a **spatial machine learning algorithm**, orchestrating a transformative intervention that challenges inequality and greed perpetuated by financial institutions.

The algorithm integrates three key inputs: **device frequencies** emanating from the building, **numeric data**, and **human traction on site**. This dynamic fusion guides a UAV's flight path, allowing for the real-time construction of an architectural street-side intervention using copper wire. The entire structure is woven by pre-programmed UAVs. This innovative process **symbolizes the appropriation of banks' unethical practices**, as participants physically acquire copper fragments during the on-site intervention commissioned by banks.

The acquired copper fragments are not just physical tokens; they undergo tokenization as **non-fungible tokens (NFTs)** through blockchain technology. This intersection of physical and digital assets empowers day traders to **engage in the digital trading market**, potentially recuperating losses and benefiting from the acquired fragments commissioned by banks.

Beyond the immediate architectural intervention, the **algorithm disrupts conventional notions of protest** by blurring public and private boundaries. Situated on banks' sites, the space becomes a **rallying point for dissent and unity** against systemic banking injustices, challenging the status quo.

REWIRE stands as a beacon of **architectural activism**, harnessing **spatial machine learning** to dynamically construct interventions that disrupt wealth accumulation cycles and reclaim financial agency. This transformative movement invites day traders to transcend traditional systems, rewrite the rules, and forge a more equitable future through the fusion of **technology, architecture, and political engagement**.

2. CONTEXT: DAYTRADING STATISTICS

Day Trading

noun// buying or selling of a security in a single trading day, aiming to make profits over short-term investments.

95% of Day Traders lose money over time.

Diagram 1: Cumulative volume of money lost by Day Traders over time.

Reasons:

- Not enough finances.
- Not enough financial resources.
- No monopoly in the stock market ladder.

Most retail Forex day traders do not survive in the market for more than a few years.

Diagram 2: Typical Journey of a Day Trader

The Forex market was originally created for Financial Giants with a minimal trade-able capital of \$10 - \$15 million. Retail traders could trade in the Forex market only after 1996.

Financial entities with the most power:

Diagram 3: Annual Trading Volume

Stock Market Power Pyramid:

Total Trading Volume = \$ 7.5 trillion per DAY

Diagram 4: Forex Market Power Pyramid

Top 10 Overall Global Market Shares:

Diagram 5: Forex Global Market Shares

The rich get richer. As seen the the Annual Trading Volume Graph, Retail investors play a very small position in the Forex daytrading market and most of them continuously lose money. Retail Investors are encouraged to 'invest' to 'take control of (their) finances' when in reality they are set to lose in the long run and help the major financial players get richer.

REWIRE is an architectural protest designed to help daytraders take back a portion of their losses from banks.

Image 1: Power exploitation visualisation (Source: Forbes)

3. ARCHITECTURAL INVESTMENT PITCH

REWIRE presents an extraordinary opportunity for banks to transcend the traditional notion of art as a financial asset, and instead embrace a pioneering data-driven sculpture that redefines architectural investments. In an era where digitalization has reduced the need for physical space to store art, REWIRE offers an avant-garde solution that allows banks to expand their art collection without compromising valuable floor and wall space.

Unlike conventional artworks confined to storage, REWIRE's sculpture exists as a dynamic, ever-evolving entity, utilizing cutting-edge data-driven techniques to embody the essence of an 'emerging artist'. This innovative intervention not only diversifies banks' investment portfolios but also sets the stage for a covert architectural protest by daytraders - a brilliant fusion of financial ingenuity and artistic rebellion.

In a world where the physical and digital realms intertwine, REWIRE's sculptural marvel blurs the lines between architecture, protest, and investment. The proposition is far more than just an architectural investment; it's a bold statement that challenges the status quo of art-financialization by allowing daytraders to use banks' thirst for power to bring the financial monopolies down.

3.1 FINANCIALIZATION OF ART

3. ARCHITECTURAL INVESTMENT

The financialisation of art refers to any **work of art** being viewed as an **asset** that is bought and sold by big financial corporations such as banks.

Today, banks have large art collections, valuing up to more than **\$50 billion** cumulatively. **JP Morgan & Chase** has the largest and oldest corporate art collection in the world, valued at **\$900 million with 30,000+ artworks**.

The very first corporate art collection was private. However, as art investments became a medium to showcase financial power, banks started having collections open to the public. While they earn from these art collections, Banks position themselves as caretakers for the art.

“We are not just the owners but the stewards of these works. It’s our duty to show and take care of them. We see ourselves as a Quasi museum.”

“Many of our clients are collectors, artists or dealers. Art is a great conversation point. It’s an interest we have in common with them.”

“Artists help open our eyes and help us view the world through a different lens”

“artists are at the pulse of what’s happening in our culture, which is why our collection always focuses on emerging artists.”

Banks also acquire art to decorate their offices. They either use artworks from their existing collections or commission artists to create site-specific art for a more personalized output. This shows the extent of their need for art to paint a more positive social image for themselves. Buying art has always been a way to boost social standing for as long as capitalism has existed, especially amongst bankers that are newly wealthy but weak in political power.

Additional Information: [Financialisation of Art Research Booklet](#)

JP Morgan & Chase will be the sample target client for the REWIRE protest.

Image 2: JP Morgan & Chase’s artwork collection library. The space has hidden bookshelves, secret stairways any unseen artwork.

Image 3. **Painting (On site mural)**
‘Chase Manhattan Bank Mural’, (1959) by Sam Francis.

Image 4. **2D Sculpture (Scratchcards)**
‘The Meeting of Two Houses’, (2015) by Basil Kincaid.

Image 5. **Digital Art**
‘Rosetta Stone, Channel 10’, (1983) by Nam June Paik.

Image 6. **Photography**
‘Nuestra Señora de las Iguanas’, (1979) by Graciela Iturbide.

Image 5. **Embroidery on Silk**
‘On the corner’, (2010) by Billie Zangewa.

Image 7. **Mixed Media**
‘I was born to love not to hate (3)’, (2017) by Alexandra Grant.

Video Link: [Investment Pitch Video for JP Morgan](#)

The marketing pitch video aims to showcase how REWIRE's unique data-driven sculpture, using the REWIRE algorithm (Section 5), offers JP Morgan a groundbreaking architectural investment that sets them apart from other banks while symbolizing their financial power.

The marketing proposal elaborates on segments covered in the pitch video.

[Marketing Proposal PDF](#)

ABOUT US
WHAT IS A REWIRE SCULPTURE?
AIMS AND OBJECTIVES
THE REWIRE SERVICE
1. PLANNING PERMISSION APPLICATION
2. MATERIALS AND CONSTRUCTION
3. MARKETING PACKAGE
FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS (FAQS) ?

4. SITE

The protest begins with using banks' corporate attitude to lure them into commissioning an **on-site, personalized, data-driven** intervention that actually lays the grounds for an **architectural protest**.

Every physical intervention is woven on a specific site. **Canary Wharf** is the location for most financial monopolies' head offices in London, including **JP Morgan's** headquarters on **25 Bank Street**.

4.1 CANARY WHARF ELEVATION

A concise history of Canary

1860

West India Docks Explos-

The area be-
came the world's
busiest shipping
port.

1980

Commercial dwinfle for the

The shipping
port and docks
saw a fall in
business and
closed commer-
cially.

1988

Construction begins

The construc-
tion of mod-
ern-day Canary
Wharf begins
with the founda-
tions being laid
for One Canada
Square.

1991

Banks move in

The primary
tenants of Ca-
nary Wharf were
HSBC, Credit
Suisse, Morgan
Stanley and Citi-
group.

1999

Mass-move

As the property market recovered from an economy crash, the stock market thrived and more financial institutions moved to Canary Wharf.

2008

Market Crash

Another market crash led to a few vacancies and external authorities look into buying Canary Wharf.

2014

Funding for further develop-

Canary Wharf Group gets acquired by external authorities and there are plans for building more commercial spaces.

2022

Expansion

Most financial authorities have their head quarters in Canary Wharf. There are plans to expand the area further east with residential spaces.

1:1500 on A2
0 50m

4.2 CANARY WHARF SITE PLAN

4.3 JP MORGAN: 25 BANK STREET ELEVATION

ENLARGED NORTH ELEVATION

1:100

Drawing Title NORTH ELEVATION	Status	Drawn By: Trip S. 10-06-2023 Checked By: Janice T. 11-06-2023 Approved By: Tim G. 12-06-2023	Scale @ A3 1:200/ 1:500	Project No. 08.6488.000	Project 25 Bank Street	Client JPMorgan Chase Bank National Association	Drawing Number 2	Revision A
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EXISTING NORTH ELEVATION

1:500

4.4 JP MORGAN: 25 BANK STREET PLAN

BANK STREET

PROPOSED INTERVENTION SITE

Drawing Title	Status	Drawn By: Trip S. 10-06-2023	Scale @ A3	Project No.	Project	Client	Drawing Number	Revision
		Checked By: Janice T. 11-06-2023	1:400	08.6488.000	25 Bank Street	JPMorgan Chase Bank National Association	5	A
		Approved By: Tim G. 12-06-2023						

JUBILEE PLACE
ATRIUM

Image 8. A section of the REWIRE intervention on JP Morgan's site.

5. REWIRE ALGORITHM

The **REWIRE Algorithm** is designed to **dynamically create a spatial intervention** using quantitative data inputs native to the bank commissioning the intervention. This example uses JP Morgan's data.

The numeric data gets converted to **spatial coordinates** and gets mapped onto JP Morgan's **street extension**. The steps of the algorithm iteratively construct the intervention over a timeframe of the **4 days and 23 hours** active trading period for banks. The construction is entirely **autonomous**, conducted by **Unmanned Automated Vehicles (UAVs)** that follow the algorithm using coordinate inputs.

The **REWIRE Algorithm** has three segments that convert data into space:

Phase 1 is site-specific, using aluminium pipes to latch onto existing architectural elements on the site.

Phase 2 is data-specific, using numeric data. It uses elastic wires to create nodes trace JP Morgan's growth over the past 3 decades.

Phase 3 is context-specific, which dynamically weaves data-nests using copper wire, based on pedestrian circulation on the site.

Simultaneous to the iterative construction, there are 3 attachments with separate functions that aid the protest:

Attachment 1: Data Nests

Attachment 2: Coordinate Nodes

Attachment 3: Seating Shards

The UAV also reads **wireless network frequencies** on the trading floors as it weaves its path and uses that as **dynamic additional input data** to create a more complicated street-level architectural installation. Therefore, the higher and the more volatile the frequency, the more aesthetic the intervention, thus attracting more human traction. The added traction is **grasped by the algorithm** and used to alter the physical intervention. Therefore, the REWIRE system works as a **spatial machine learning model** that becomes a **strong tool for socio-politic commentary** against unethical capitalist exploiters in the society.

5.1 IDENTIFYING ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS

Common street furniture and building latches are used to provide coordinates for Phase 1 of the algorithm, where primary lathes are attached.

Building-specific architectural elements for 25 Bank Street include:

- Hollow facade pipes
- Street overhangs
- CCTV casings
- Wall-mounted lamps

Common street furniture found in Canary Wharf includes:

- Lamp posts
- Traffic signals
- Planters

Street Signs

Appendix 2 shows site-images.

Additional vertical and horizontal elements on the facade:

The REWIRE algorithm converts any numerical data to a spatial intervention on a given site.

The data is modulated, mapped and translated onto the site using vector coordinates, which are materialised into a spatial artefact using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs).

The site is first converted into a 3D cartesian coordinate grid.

Next, the UAV scans the site and identifies architectural latches, outlined on previous pages, and extracts coordinates.

1. PRIMARY ELEMENTS

50 mm'' Aluminium pipes

Phase 1 is site-specific, using aluminium pipes to latch onto existing architectural elements on the site.

2. COORDINATE NODES

Rubber friction clip with 10 mm'' elastic rope attached to stainless steel ring nodes

Phase 2 is data-specific, using numeric data. It uses elastic wires to create nodes trace JP Morgan's growth over the past 3 decades.

3. INTERSECTION NODE

2 mm'' copper wire

Phase 3 is context-specific, which dynamically weaves data-nests using copper wire, based on pedestrian circulation on the site.

5.4 ALGORITHM EXPLANATION

The technical elevation and algorithm explanation sheet outline all steps of the REWIRE algorithm in detail with coordinates for each phase.

Primary Element [P _i]	Coordinate [x,y,z]	Primary Element [P _j]	Coordinate [x,y,z]
P1	14444, 61, 6951	P19	55741, 2173, 1015
P2	14444, 61, 9979	P20	49501, 5000, 696
P3	28444, 61, 6951	P21	21509, 5000, 696
P4	28444, 61, 9979	P22	28499, 5000, 696
P5	42444, 61, 6951	P23	27800, 2700, 11100
P6	42444, 61, 9979	P24	29200, 2700, 11100
P7	56498, 5000, 10243	P25	15200, 2700, 11100
P8	56498, 5000, 5574	P26	41800, 2700, 11100
P9	42495, 5000, 5574	P27	7507, 5000, 696
P10	28518, 5000, 5574	P28	14445, 490, 1758
P11	14494, 5000, 5574	P29	28444, 490, 1758
P12	497, 5000, 5574	P30	42443, 490, 1758
P13	500, 5000, 10243	P31	42443, 490, 10108
P14	2244, 1791, 1300	P32	28444, 490, 10108
P15	10707, 2586, 1370	P33	14445, 490, 10108
P16	21171, 2173, 1015	P34	55741, 2173, 1015
P17	35501, 5000, 696	P35	21509, 5000, 696
P18	35818, 2173, 1015	P36	29465, 380, 584
Node Element [C _i]	Coordinate [x,y,z]	Node Element [C _j]	Coordinate [x,y,z]
C1	9117, 4743, 4450	C6	35143, 4142, 10324
C1a	7612, 3465, 1948	C6a	36028, 2662, 9743
C1b	6297, 4882, 2632	C6b	36043, 2894, 9716
C1c	8525, 3894, 2116	C6c	34711, 5787, 5167
C1d	8370, 5397, 3740	C6d	33449, 4481, 2420
C2	12289, 1602, 5665	C6e	34675, 1494, 2700
C2a	11358, 4585, 2794	C6f	35497, 1104, 8965
C2b	12312, 4957, 6569	C7	42021, 3152, 4140
C2c	14025, 5340, 6219	C7a	42101, 5591, 5702
C2d	11771, 5092, 6974	C7b	40681, 2069, 8400
C2e	16005, 5392, 1814	C7c	39789, 1626, 1803
C3	16309, 4603, 4709	C7d	40732, 587, 4315
C3a	17970, 4897, 10471	C7e	38394, 2338, 3309
C3b	17748, 1363, 3688	C7f	40845, 5692, 2055
C3c	16262, 5062, 5475	C7g	38383, 3529, 2969
C3d	17394, 5908, 1108	C7h	41026, 4117, 5607
C3e	17840, 3899, 10004	C8	46488, 1058, 7562
C3f	15514, 624, 10725	C8a	41113, 5879, 8033
C3g	17364, 5736, 6697	C8b	44590, 3733, 8364
C4	21294, 1352, 8080	C8c	43033, 4336, 8476
C4a	20283, 2789, 3679	C8d	43025, 563, 1515
C4b	20973, 2288, 1997	C8e	42020, 1518, 10568
C4c	20581, 3561, 4796	C8f	41117, 4598, 1034
C4d	21376, 388, 5871	C8g	45050, 3707, 4618
C4e	20004, 2178, 3562	C8h	45137, 1964, 10696
C4f	20111, 3405, 2093	C8i	43932, 309, 5141
C5	25236, 2566, 7502	C8j	42841, 2041, 1391
C5a	22920, 4838, 6358	C8k	45181, 127, 3660
C5b	26609, 482, 4193	C9	55279, 1944, 4994
Nest Element [N1 _i]	Coordinate [x,y,z]	Nest Element [N1 _j]	Coordinate [x,y,z]
N1a	5385, 5640, 2332	N1n	2722, 1116, 1315
N1b	3368, 5809, 1292	N1o	1467, 5168, 2301
N1c	4749, 1887, 3061	N1p	5463, 3992, 1741
N1d	5577, 5534, 1405	N1q	4228, 2938, 2640
N1e	3966, 2100, 974	N1r	1879, 2343, 1504
N1f	3290, 5971, 1817	N1s	939, 1152, 2289
N1g	4856, 3832, 1283	N1t	4072, 3117, 1098
N1h	5531, 1065, 1938	N1u	5127, 4053, 2884
N1i	4251, 4342, 2921	N1v	3402, 2756, 1402
N1j	2558, 4037, 982	N1w	5764, 3994, 2912
N1k	1871, 3329, 2043	N1x	3595, 4252, 2501
N1l	3119, 1120, 2431	N1y	1176, 1016, 1612
N1m	996, 2215, 1604	N1z	3070, 5739, 3202
Nest Element [N2 _i]	Coordinate [x,y,z]	Nest Element [N2 _j]	Coordinate [x,y,z]
N2a	25452, 5110, 5045	N2n	26932, 2414, 7736
N2b	28503, 3212, 5215	N2o	26980, 4450, 4658
N2c	28592, 2906, 4962	N2p	26605, 1561, 7884
N2d	26917, 4022, 5026	N2q	29726, 5288, 8146
N2e	29424, 846, 5115	N2r	29182, 3888, 7475
N2f	27741, 5283, 5084	N2s	25025, 3670, 7423
N2g	27625, 1749, 6003	N2t	30367, 1285, 5480
N2h	27008, 2834, 7483	N2u	25361, 3821, 6723
N2i	25915, 2911, 7328	N2v	26000, 4232, 4837
N2j	30378, 3574, 5942	N2w	25134, 3310, 5023
N2k	29371, 2098, 5679	N2x	29657, 3658, 7551
N2l	27160, 4976, 7587	N2y	28228, 4980, 8021
N2m	27026, 5283, 7010	N2z	26094, 4981, 6830
Nest Element [N3 _i]	Coordinate [x,y,z]	Nest Element [N3 _j]	Coordinate [x,y,z]
N3a	54811, 2832, 4014	N3n	54466, 3589, 5103
N3b	55096, 4275, 2043	N3o	55458, 4257, 5218
N3c	53994, 4381, 4281	N3p	53406, 3531, 2736
N3d	51164, 2826, 4812	N3q	51955, 3132, 3386
N3e	53399, 3728, 1538	N3r	52563, 3503, 1972
N3f	52498, 2879, 3212	N3s	53294, 3185, 3090
N3g	51815, 3959, 1433	N3t	52321, 3600, 2192
N3h	54598, 2773, 2663	N3u	53026, 3296, 4043
N3i	52022, 4186, 4526	N3v	54106, 3927, 4340
N3j	52678, 4137, 3823	N3w	51807, 2687, 5090
N3k	52631, 3333, 4419	N3x	53338, 3091, 1800
N3l	53086, 2755, 4819	N3y	52306, 2966, 4170
N3m	53671, 3001, 2510	N3z	52841, 3280, 4593
Nest Centre	Data Nest 1 (N1)	Data Nest 2 (N2)	Data Nest 3 (N3)
Coordinate [x,y,z]	2550, 2500, 2975	2700, 2400, 1825	2000, 900, 2000

1. Identifying existing architectural elements

Plotting **one coordinate** on each architectural latch (ex. base of a planter, overhangs, offset elements, lamp post base)

2. Connecting existing architectural elements to create the primary structural net [P_i].

Material: **Aluminium tubes, 5mm'** with specialised **carabiner hooks**.

Note: Primary elements are represented by [P_i] on the Technical Elevation and Data Sheet.

3. Converting numerical datasets to coordinates.

X - axis: Time (scaled to the **length** of the site)
Y - axis: Revenue (per year) [scaled to the **width** of the site]
Z - axis: Variable dataset [scaled to the **height** of the site]

Choosing 10 data points to trace the company's growth curve.

- Constructed data coordinate
- Chosen data coordinate

4. Calculating shortest distance to an existing phase 1 elements.

Every coordinate is projected on each primary element to calculate the nearest element.

$$D = \frac{\| \overline{QP} \times \overline{QR} \|}{\| \overline{QR} \|}$$

Note: The coordinates shown here are only examples and do not correspond to a real site.

5. Projecting each coordinate onto 10 closest phase 1 elements [C_i].

From C₁ to C₁₀, the 10 closest projection will be materialized into adjustable nodes.

Material: **Elastic cables (2.5mm)** with **rubber friction clips**.

6. Data Nests [D_i]: Placement

The site is divided into three zones A_i, spanning maximum 20m. Each zone has one data nest.

7. Data Nests: Base Conical Forms

Each Data Nest (D_i) is constructed using a base conical form:

$$\text{Radius } (r) = [A_n * (x + y)] / [\Sigma x_n + \Sigma y_n]$$

$$\text{Height } (h) = [A_n * z] / [\Sigma x_n]$$

$$\text{Position } (X_n, Y_n, Z_n): [A_n * \Sigma x_n / n], [A_n * \Sigma y_n / n], [A_n * \Sigma z_n / n]$$

8. Data Nests: Distorted Conical Forms

Based on the site, each base conical geometry is distorted:

$$\text{Twist angle } (^\circ) = [\Sigma x_n + \Sigma y_n + \Sigma z_n] / n$$

$$\text{Bend angle } (^\circ) = [\Sigma x_n + \Sigma y_n + \Sigma z_n] / \Sigma A_n$$

9. Data Nests: Cone to Polygon Deconstruction

The cone is deconstructed to individual faces to create a polygonal form.

D₁ = 5000 x 5000 x 2300 D₂ = 5200 x 5200 x 3700 D₃ = 4000 x 4000 x 1800

Each polygon has a scaled box around it, to facilitate weaving.

10. Data Nests: Mapping Pedestrian Data

The deconstructed form is materialised into a mesh based on:

1. Average speed
2. Vector direction
3. Average pausing / moving time
4. Pausing coordinate

The numeric data is mapped onto the scale box and converted to a vector input for the UAV.

Material: **Copper wire 3 mm'**

10. Data Nest Connection Links

Most active segments of the nests are connected to primary links using the shortest distance formula.

5.7 ENGAGEMENT ELEMENT 1: COORDINATE NODES

Coordinate nodes from phase 2 have friction clips that can be reattached to either the primary aluminium tubes or other coordinate rings.

These are elements that draw pedestrians into the space because they can reorganise the intervention and therefore gain a sense of freedom.

Front Elevation: Identifying Coordinate Nodes

Metal Ring Core:

ISOMETRIC

PLAN

ELEVATION

Cable Attachment:

Rubber Friction Clip:
Attaches onto any 'coordinate ring' or primary structural element.

ALTERING A SINGLE ELEMENT:

Every 'Cable' element with the friction rubber latch can be altered and attached to another 'ring' node or primary element.

5.8 ENGAGEMENT ELEMENT 2: SEATING SHARDS

The second engagement feature are seating elements that are shaped like shards and made of aluminium to reflect banks' corporate nature and are elevated at angles that help facilitate seating and leaning.

PLAN

ELEVATION

SHARD POSITIONS

Horizontal Aluminium panels (10.00 mm)

The aluminium panels bend according to human interaction with the seating shard.

1:200 ON A3

6. ARCHITECTURAL INTERVENTION

This section shows architectural drawings and visualisations of the resulting space once JP Morgan's quantitative data is processed through the REWIRE algorithm and converted to a spatial intervention. The architectural drawings are accompanied by a physical model and digital visualisations to try and realise the intervention in reference to the site.

6.1 DETAILED ELEVATION

5700

Drawing Title
**PROPOSED NORTH
ELEVATION**

Status

Drawn By: Trip S. 10-06-2023
Checked By: Janice T. 11-06-2023
Approved By: Tim C. 12-06-2023

Scale @ A3
1:100
0 2.5m

Project No.
08.6488.000

Project
25 Bank Street

Client
JPMorgan Chase Bank
National Association

Drawing Number
4

Revision
A

- Site-specific: Primary Elements
- Data-driven: Coordinate Nodes and Ele-
- Context-driven: Pedestrian Data Nests

6.2 DETAILED PLAN

57

Drawing Title
**ENLARGED PROPOSED
 PLAN**

Status

Drawn By: Trip S. 10-06-2023
 Checked By: Janice T. 11-06-2023
 Approved By: Tim C. 12-06-2023

Scale @ A3

1:100
0 1 2 3 4 5 2.5m

Project No.

08.6488.000

Project

25 Bank Street

Client

JPMorgan Chase Bank
 National Association

Drawing Number

6

Revision

A

2000

000

- Site-specific: Primary Elements
- Data-driven: Coordinate Nodes and Ele-
- Context-driven: Pedestrian Data Nests

6.3 VISUALISATIONS

These visualisations show the architectural intervention as a streetside extension to JP Morgan's **25 Bank Street** site in Canary Wharf. The views show aluminium pipes (**phase 1**), elastic cables (**phase 2**), copper wire and data nests (**phase 3**), coordinate nodes and seating shards at different times of the day.

6.4 MODEL IMAGES

The physical model attempts at exploring how the logical flow of the algorithm intertwines with physical materiality. The model represents **1/3 of the front facade** to explore all elements in detail.

Phase 1 pipes: Represented by **thick silver wire**.

Phase 2 cables: Represented by **thin silver wire**.

Phase 3 wires: Represented by **bronze wire and resin**.

An [animation](#) showing how elements of REWIRE algorithm phase 3 data nests can be acquired over time by protestors.

Note: Please follow the link to view the animation.

7. PROTEST: ARCHITECTURAL ACQUISITION

REWIRE's algorithm embodies **redundancy**, ingeniously woven to empower participants of the protest with unique agency. Dubbed "**breaking points**," these strategically designed elements allow protesters to acquire sections of the architectural intervention without jeopardizing its **stability**. Each "acquired" piece becomes a **digital asset**, tokenized on the REWIRE platform as an **NFT**, enabling **protesters to profit** from the very sculpture commissioned by banks.

Participating in this **choreographed process**, protesters select a piece on the REWIRE platform and choose their desired "breaking time." At the designated moment, a drone envelops them in a veil of mist, creating 30 seconds of transparency, ostensibly to engage pedestrians. However, this mist serves a dual purpose - it provides a **discreet opportunity** for protesters to seize their chosen copper fragment, fostering a **covert act of empowerment** within the dynamic streetside spectacle.

Protesters follow pre-organised circulation paths, acquire pre-identified copper segments in order to **physically redesign the intervention** to the final phase of the protest: **architectural collapse**.

7.1 BREAKING POINTS ISOMETRIC

The REWIRE platform provides protestors with a 3D map of all **redundant copper elements** integrated into the space through the REWIRE algorithm - either alterable or acquirable. **Acquirable** for protestors, **alterable** for pedestrians.

- Detachable link for acquirable and alterable elements

Protestors can choose what elements they want to 'acquire' and set a 'breaking time'. On the chosen time, UAVs are preprogrammed to shield protestors with 30 seconds of transparency behind mist to snap the chosen piece and walk away.

7.2 PEDESTRIAN CIRCULATION

The REWIRE algorithm phase 3 has data nests which are altered based on pedestrian circulation. Therefore, there is a **pre-laid circulation path** for protesters to follow, to lead phase 3 in a pre-designed manner.

Following the given circulation will help after phase 3 in an iterative manner, which will help **reorganise the architectural intervention** for the final **physical collapse**.

7.3 PEDESTRIAN INTERACTION

The plan, front elevation, and right elevation on this unfolded drawing show a time-based interaction between pedestrians and protestors within the same architectural intervention.

- Person 1: **Protestor**
- Person 2: **Pedestrian**
- Opaque Path: Stealing Act
- Dotted Path: Interaction Act

7.4 REWIRE PLATFORM

At its core, REWIRE is a protest. These are poster drafts for REWIRE, attracting daytraders to join the REWIRE protest.

The first step is to create an account and then they can access the following features through the platform:

1. Breaking Points 3D map
2. Choosing a time for acquiring the chosen copper element.
3. REWIRE Tokenisation tool
4. REWIRE Marketplace
4. List of participants and user IDs
5. Link to social media platforms
6. Access to a live update for JP Morgan data feeding the intervention.

The intervention gets more aesthetically pleasing with more data. Therefore, JP Morgan can choose to provide proprietary data to enhance pedestrian traffic. Regardless, protestors have direct data to JP Morgan's profits, clients and other data that quantifies their position and exploitation of power.

7.5 TOKENISATION PROCESS

Protesters connect with the movement through the online REWIRE platform, which provides them access to the REWIRE Marketplace. The marketplace shows information about protestors selling their acquired segments.

On the REWIRE platform, protestors can:

1. Choose and acquire their 'acquired' fragment.
2. Tokenise the fragment.
3. Set a selling price for their NFT on the REWIRE marketplace.
4. Keep all their profits from their NFT.

#	COLLECTION	BREAKING POINT NUMBER	FLOOR PRICE	VOLUME	VOLUME CHANGE	ITEMS	OWNERS
1	TripTrade	15	10.29 ETH	1,726 ETH	+184.2%	19.5K	11.9K
2	TradingCanyon	7	46.91 ETH	1,065 ETH	+335.3%	10K	6K
3	CodeWhizTrader	159	8.88 ETH	693.7 ETH	+395.5%	10K	4.6K
4	PixelPips	74	4.2 ETH	362.8 ETH	+90.2%	10K	3.5K
5	TradingAlgo	2	1.269 ETH	316.1 ETH	+447.8%	26.8K	10K
6	CodingWolf	19	4.75 ETH	227.4 ETH	-8.2%	8.9K	4.8K
7	ByteTrading	64	1.528 ETH	182.6 ETH	+32.2%	10K	2.5K
8	TradeTechPro	23	3.35 ETH	164.9 ETH	+29.8%	10K	3.1K
9	BinaryWhiz	17	8.6 ETH	130 ETH	-48.9%	8.7K	1.7K
10	CodeBaron	12	14.99 ETH	120.3 ETH	-68.2%	10K	4.8K

Protesters also have the potential to trade NFTs to help modulate demand and supply and consequently help give rise to further expanding the REWIRE movement. This can ultimately help the architectural protest's aim:

Exploiting and revealing corporate banks' unethical practices.

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---- Alterable Tensile Elements
— Remaining Acquirable Copper Elements

An [animation](#) showing the final phase of the REWIRE protest: **Architectural Collapse**.

Note: Please follow the link to view the animation.

8. PROTEST: ARCHITECTURAL COLLAPSE

As the culmination of a meticulously orchestrated protest, this phase marks a pivotal moment in the dynamic fusion of **architecture, data, and rebellion**.

On **April 5** at **16:29**, precisely chosen as the end of the financial year, protestors execute a masterstroke, eliminating all 'acquirable' elements from the physical REWIRE intervention, setting the site for a dramatic finale. Unpredictable to JP Morgan, this collapse is triggered by **drones** discreetly **unlatching primary elements** from the existing architectural infrastructure, ultimately leading to the **stunning collapse** of the entire intervention. The aftermath reverberates with waves of **negative publicity**, sparking a potential revolution against **unethical corporate financial practices**, echoing the spirit of the Occupy Wall Street movement at a larger, grander, and more **transparent architectural scale**.

8. UAV WEAVING SCHEDULE

The UAV weaving schedule follows the trading hours for **London Stock Exchange**. The base construction of the intervention occurs upon receiving the commission. Thereafter, the intervention is dynamically updated onsite using pedestrian traffic as data input.

UAVs weave across 2 times of the day: **Market Start [0800]** and **Market End [1630]**. These are the most volatile trading periods of the day, potentially disrupted by UAV movement.

Active Period 1: **0800 - 0830**

Dormant Period: 0830 - 1600

[The spatial algorithm then gathers data throughout the day.]

Active Period 2: **1600 - 1630**

Final Collapse occurs at 16:29 on April 5, the end of the financial year.

- Market Start: Weaving period 1
- Market End: Weaving period 2
- UAV Inactive
- UAV Active

8. 'PRE-COLLAPSE' POSITION

On the REWIRE Platform, protestors' main goal is to change the intervention from the initial state to the pre-collapse position.

Initial design.

Once all protestors have successfully acquired and altered the intervention to its pre-collapse design, the primary aluminium supports are changed to a state of high tension. This helps the entire intervention eventually collapse at the street level.

Pre-collapse Design.

The intervention collapse will definitely block the building entrance in the short run, but over time it will yield a lot of negative publicity through a social media protest on platforms like Reddit.

As the collapse occurs at **16:29 on April 5**, RIGHT before the financial year ends and the end-of-year statements are released. Therefore, the collapse will also affect JP Morgan's stock price, insurance and financial costs as well as investor sentiments.

Reddit Screenshot: Promoting REWIRE through a social media revolt.

REWIRE

[An Architectural Protest Against Banks]

22:00 [7] - 21:00 [5]

rewire.io

Smart Money

The return of the buy back bid in 2025.

JOHN AULTERS, PAGE 54

Driving Growth

Canary Wharf Banks Forge Strategic Partnerships

JAMIL ANDERINI, PAGE 17

Enhancing Trust in Forex

The Role of Blockchain Technology

KATHERINE PLAIGE, PAGE 32

Unprecedented Architectural Collapse Shakes JP Morgan

REWIRE Sculpture, a Public Engagement Effort, Turns into an Unexpected Protest.

TRIP TRADEMAN

In recent years, the financial industry has faced numerous ethical challenges, ranging from forex rate manipulation to unfair market practices, casting doubt on the integrity of banking institutions. Amidst this backdrop, JP Morgan's ambitious architectural sculpture, REWIRE, was commissioned as a bid to improve the bank's corporate image while showcasing its wealth. However, this grand endeavor took an unexpected turn on April 6, 2025, as the entire sculpture collapsed, obstructing the exit of JP Morgan's prestigious 25 Bank Street site. This catastrophe not only caused financial losses but also raised questions about the consequences of unethical practices.

REWIRE, a colossal street-side sculpture constructed using drones and woven with copper wire based on JP Morgan's data, captured the public's attention. The interactive nature of the sculpture allowed pedestrians to engage and reorganize its elements, while the drones diligently continued their weaving spectacle during trading hours, creating a mesmerizing show that drew in more passersby.

The sculpture success in engaging the public cannot be denied. Foot traffic surged as people flocked to witness this innovative fusion of art, technology, and finance. Statistical data revealed a substantial increase in the number of visitors, amplifying the visibility of JP Morgan's brand and presence within the community.

However, as the financial year drew to a close on that fateful day, the REWIRE sculpture collapsed unexpectedly, bringing chaos and disruption.

The collapsed street intervention outside JP Morgan's 25 Bank Street Headquarters.

The collapse not only blocked the exit of JP Morgan's premises but also caused severe repercussions throughout the financial landscape. The density of the copper wire employed in the sculpture interfered with Wi-Fi signals, leading to significant communication disruptions and costing the bank a staggering 2.1 billion GBP. The ensuing financial turmoil further resulted in a noticeable drop in JP Morgan's stock price, compounding the consequences of this unforeseen event.

The collapse of the REWIRE sculpture represents more than just a physical disaster, it serves as a symbolic awakening for the banking industry.

It underscores the need for ethical practices, transparency, and genuine efforts to regain public trust. The juxtaposition of this incident against the backdrop of unethical banking practices, such as forex rate manipulation, magnifies the repercussions of a market that favors a select few while leaving day traders and ordinary investors vulnerable.

As the financial world reflects on this unprecedented event, it is crucial to address the underlying issues that allowed such a protest to manifest. The collapse of REWIRE serves as a stark reminder that the public demands accountability and fairness in the financial sector. While the true

implications of this incident are yet to unfold fully, it undeniably represents a turning point in the relationship between banks and society. As the dust settles, the banking industry must reassess its practices, prioritize ethical conduct, and rebuild trust with the public.

Only by embracing a culture of equality, transparency, and full accountability can banks not only restore stability and safeguard their reputation but also pave the way for a future that prioritizes the empowerment of day traders and ensures that the impact of unethical banking practices is fully revealed and addressed for the benefit of each

individual within the financial ecosystem. In recent years, the financial industry has faced numerous ethical challenges, ranging from forex rate manipulation to unfair market practices, casting doubt on the integrity of banking institutions. Amidst this backdrop, JP Morgan's ambitious architectural sculpture, REWIRE, was commissioned as a bid to improve the bank's corporate image while showcasing its wealth.

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JP Morgan's Jamie Dimon sought for interview in Jeffrey Epstein lawsuit

In a significant development that has attracted widespread attention, Jamie Dimon, the CEO of JP Morgan Chase, has been requested for a second interview regarding his interactions with the late financier and convicted sex offender, Jeffrey Epstein. The lawsuit, which accuses JP Morgan of facilitating Epstein's financial activities, seeks further clarity on the extent of the bank's involvement.

Big read, page 15.

Unveiling the Deception: CEO Scandal Shakes HSBC investors and Employee Trust

SALLY MENGET

In a shocking revelation that has reverberated throughout the financial industry, a CEO scandal has come to light within the ranks of HSBC, one of the world's leading banks. This distressing development has sent shockwaves through the organization and beyond, deeply impacting employee trust and the bank's reputation. As the intricate details of this fraudulent scheme unfold, it raises important questions about the adequacy of existing safeguards and the overall corporate culture within HSBC.

At the core of this scandal lies the alleged involvement of the bank's CEO in a deceptive scheme that has left employees financially compro-

mised and emotionally devastated. The breach of trust stemming from these actions has had profound consequences, undermining the very foundations of HSBC and raising significant concerns about the ethical standards upheld within the institution.

The fallout from the CEO scandal extends far beyond the monetary losses suffered by employees. It has dealt a severe blow to employee morale, leaving hardworking individuals grappling with a profound sense of insecurity. The breach of trust not only affects the impacted employees directly but also has wider implications for the overall organizational climate and employee engagement.

The HSBC scandal has cast a critical spotlight on the need for robust internal controls and governance mechanisms within the banking industry. Financial institutions across the board must seize this moment as an opportunity to reevaluate their own systems, fortify safeguards, and ensure a culture of transparency and integrity prevails. Rebuilding trust in the aftermath of such a scandal is an arduous task that requires immediate and resolute action from HSBC. It necessitates addressing the concerns and grievances of affected employees in a timely and compassionate manner, providing the necessary support and compensation.

Big read, page 11.

Goldman Sachs E-COMMERCE

Percent change relative to January 2022

62% Users are influenced by social media.

Users are influenced by their friends. 29%

Online's share of total retail sales has increased rapidly. Explore Goldman Sachs E-Commerce!

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NO. 50476

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World Markets

STOCK MARKET			CURRENCIES				INTEREST RATES				
Name	Price	Change	Major	EUR	JPY	GBP	USD	Country	2-year yield	10-year yield	
S&P 500	4305.33	+0.27%	1 GBP	1.1701	175.20	1.000	1.2577				
Dow	35895.11	+0.18%	1 EUR	1.0000	149.72	0.8545	1.0748	Europe	2.97%	2.57%	
FT 5000	45465.81	+0.16%	1 USD	0.9305	159.50	0.7950	1.0000				
Nikkei	32265.17	+1.97%	1 AUD	0.6269	95.87	0.5358	0.6739	Japan	-0.06%	0.44%	
Hang Seng	19589.95	+0.47%	COMMODITIES								
DAX	15949.84	-0.25%	Commodities		Last price/contract	Today's change					
FTSE 100	7562.36	-0.49%	Coffee (Arabica)		191.45	-1.74%	United Kingdom	4.54%	4.24%		
TSX Comp	19888.78	-0.27%	As of Jun 12 2025		USc		United States	4.60%	3.75%		
NASDAQ	15285.38	+0.35%	Natural Gas		2.26	-3.91%	Canada	3.25%	3.15%		
JSE	76956.11	-0.10%	As of Jun 12 2025		USD		Switzerland	3.50%	3.34%		
Eurofirst	1819.55	-0.20%	Corn		604.50	-0.94%					
CAC 40	7215.14	-0.12%	As of Jun 12 2025		USc						
RTS	1032.29	-0.05%	Brent Crude Oil		74.88	-0.08%	Sweden	3.50%	3.00%		
CNX Nifty	18565.40	-0.38%	As of Jun 12 2025		USD						
Topix	2224.32	+1.50%									

The aftermath of the REWIRE intervention's collapse on JP Morgan's street-side is nothing short of seismic. The dense web of copper, once an architectural marvel, now becomes a formidable blockade, rendering the building entrance impassable. Moreover, the intricate copper structure wreaks havoc on wireless signals, causing unpredictable fluctuations in communication and trading systems within the financial district.

However, the physical implications pale in comparison to the storm of negative publicity that ensues. The collapse becomes a viral sensation on social media, with the world witnessing the dramatic consequences of a complex architectural intervention, woven using the very financial profit exploitation that defines JP Morgan's operations. As the news spreads like wildfire, the impact reverberates through the stock market, resulting in significant fluctuations in JP Morgan's stock price and end-of-year financial statements.

The revelation of unethical banking practices on such a grand scale shakes the financial industry to its core, igniting a public outcry against corporate malpractices. The REWIRE intervention, once an artistic and data-driven masterpiece, now serves as a catalyst for a massive paradigm shift, pushing society to confront the dark underbelly of financial institutions. The fallout from the collapse sets in motion a domino effect that may forever reshape the dynamics of modern banking, echoing the fervor and significance of the Occupy Wall Street movement on a much larger, more transparent, and influential stage.

REWIRE Process Summary:

Step 1: Marketing Proposal to Banks

Step 2: Monitoring the construction of the Rewire intervention

Step 3: Viewing the 3D 'Breaking Point' map

Step 4: Choosing a physical segment to 'acquire'

Step 5: Choosing a 'Breaking Time'

Step 6: Going to the site, hiding behind a wall of mist, acquiring the segment.

Step 7: Tokenising and selling the segment as an NFT on the Rewire marketplace.

Step 8: Collectively acquire copper elements in a pattern that helps shift the intervention to its pre-collapse position by 16:29 on April 5.

Step 9: Post-collapse, generate a viral social media revolution against banks' exploitation of capitalistic power.

9. UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE (UAV) MOVEMENT

This section describes studies on drone motion which will inform the development of the weaving algorithm.

- Physical tests were conducted using a **manually-controlled test drone**.
- The weaving motion for **loops and knots** to create nodes across linear and surface structures was tested and documented.
- Different materials were used to simulate copper wire, including **elastic string**, **sewing thread** and **9-gauge guitar wire**.

While physical tests informed specifications of UAV motion dynamics, **digital tests were used to simulate point-following and obstacle avoidance**. The logic behind the obstacle-avoidance programming can be embedded into the path-following algorithm for the drone to ensure that the intervention is continuously growing over its active period while being safe.

9.1 UAV VECTOR MOTION

A UAV works with a North-East-Down coordinate system. This can be represented using Euler angles and the X-Y-Z coordinate system.

UAV position vector: [x, y, z]

+ve [z] indicates altitude gain and -ve [z] indicates altitude loss.

The UAV body frame is attached to its centre of mass with coordinates [x_b, y_b, z_b]. x_b is the preferred forward direction. All code will use it as the default direction to align the UAV's head. Z_b is the vertical direction and is perpendicular to the x-y plane.

Forces acting on a UAV:

1. **Weight:** The body mass force for the UAV always acts in the direction of gravity.
2. **Vertical Force:** Lift works against gravity and is provided by the UAV propellers.
3. **Thrust:** Thrust is always normal to the rotor plant and acts in the direction of motion.
4. **Drag:** Acts opposite to the direction of motion due to air resistance.

Diagram 14: Forces acting on a UAV.

Considerations for UAV motion:

Table 5 outlines concepts important to kinematic vector motion physics, specifically in reference to UAV motion.

Property	Units	Description
World Position (x, y, z)	m	[x, y, z] coordinate on the vector plane.
Euler Angles (zyx)	radians	[psi, phi, theta]: A three dimensional rotations by three separate rotations on individual axis.
Height	m	Height above the X-Y plane.
Air Speed	m/s	Drone speed relative to the wind speed.
Heading Angle	radians	Angle between ground velocity and North.
Flight Path Angle	radians	Angle between the ground velocity and North-East (X-Y) plane.
Roll Angle	radians/s	Angle of rotation along the UAV body x-axis.
Roll Angle Rate	radians/s	Angular velocity of rotation along the UAV body x-axis.

Table 5: Kinematic vector motion terminologies

UAV Controls:

1. **Hover:** Up and down movement.
2. **Yaw:** Rotating left and right.
3. **Roll:** Bending left and right.
4. **Pitch:** Forward and backward movement.

Drone Dynamics Equation:

$$\begin{matrix} \text{Total Force} \\ \begin{pmatrix} F \\ T \end{pmatrix} \\ \text{Total} \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} \text{Total Mass} \\ \begin{bmatrix} M & 0_B \\ 0_B & I \end{bmatrix} \\ \text{Total Iner-} \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \text{Linear Acceleration} \\ \begin{bmatrix} a \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} \\ \text{Angular} \end{matrix} + \begin{matrix} \text{Linear Veloc-} \\ \begin{bmatrix} \omega \times mv \\ \omega \times I\omega \end{bmatrix} \\ \text{Angular Ve-} \\ \text{Angular Accelera-} \end{matrix}$$

Diagram 15: Controls for a UAV.

9. UAV WEAVING STRUCTURAL TYPOLOGIES

A woven intervention using UAVs is constructed using **three types of structural typologies**:

Each typology can be used on its own, but using multiple typologies together provides a space with higher spatial complexity within **phases 1, 2 and 3**.

1. Linear Structure

A linear structure uses existing structural elements (ex. Columns, Overlays, Beams, etc...) as a base for construction. It attaches two nodes to the structural elements, along one axis. The construction is independent of ground conditions.

2. Surface Structure

Surface structures are two-dimensional intersections of linear structures. They connect nodes along two or more linear structures along any common axis. The UAV weaves through existing structures, demonstrating their potential to **simultaneously construct and manipulate a space**.

3. Volumetric Structure

Volumetric structures are three dimensional intersections of linear structures. Either connecting a surface structure and a linear structure at different altitudes or connecting three linear structures in non-parallel axis, both create volumetric structures. Multiple UAVs can **weave together to create volumetric structures**

9. PHYSICAL TEST 1: BASIC DRONE MOVEMENT

Tests 1A - 1F show weaving tests around fixed copper wires. Different thread types were used instead of copper wires because the focus was to test weaving motion led by the drone. The aim was to check how the weight of the weaving material affects drone motion, which will inform the final weaving material thickness.

TEST A

Drone test A shows the drone attempting a weaving motion around **one fixed copper wire**, without any attachments. There is **no drift or lag** in the drone's motion.

TEST B

Weaving Material: White **Sewing Thread**
Thickness: **0.10 mm** diameter

Drone test B shows the drone attempting a weaving motion around one fixed copper wire using a knitted sewing thread. The drone could **easily carry** the sewing thread's weight. However, the thread **slips on the wire**.

TEST C

Weaving Material: **Black Elastic Thread**
Thickness: **1.2 mm** diameter

Three iterations using the same thread are shown. The 1.2 mm diameter thread is **too heavy** for the drone to carry, in addition to its own weight. It is unable to weave **beyond one loop**, as seen in all three iterations of Test C. It **starts lagging**, which leads to **a tilt** and in consequence, the **thread gets entangled** between the drone's propellers.

9. UAV MOVEMENT Physical Drone Test

— Fixed Copper Wire

Note: All tests follow a hand-controlled drone.

TEST D

Weaving Material: Black **Elastic Thread**
Thickness: **1.0 mm** diameter

Drone Test D shows the drone attempting to weave a black thread (1 mm diameter) around a **single copper wire**. The drone holds the weight of the black thread well, **without deviating** too much with additional weight. In comparison to test 1, there was **more friction** between the copper wire and elastic thread, leading to **less slipping** and a **more stable contact connection**.

TEST E

Test E adds an **additional fixed copper wire**. From test 1 - 4, the drone performed best with the thin sewing thread but visually it was not visible and slipped over the copper wires easily. The **black thread** provided a **more interesting output**. Therefore, test 6 will be performed using the black thread.

TEST E

Weaving Material: Black **Elastic Thread**
Thickness: **1.0 mm** diameter

Test F shows the drone attempting to weave around **two fixed copper wires** using a black thread. The second fixed copper wire is **diagonal** on plan and elevation, thus **adding complexity** to the weaving playing field. The drone could weave **two loops** without its trajectory getting affected, after which the **higher volume** of thread **added weight** and consequently led to a **wavering, unstable motion**.

9. PHYSICAL TEST 2: WEAVING MOVEMENT USING WIRES

9 gauge guitar wires were used for Test 2. The test drone is unable to carry higher loads so the guitar strings allow for a close simulation to actual copper wire. Guitar strings bend and behave similar to thin copper wires.

Test 2A: Two fixed copper wire nodes
Weaving a fishing wire around **two fixed linear elements** to create a 2D surface structure.

Process:
Single loop (top element) -> Single loop (bottom element) -> Double loop (top element).

[Test 2A Video](#)

Test 2B: Two fixed linear copper wire nodes with a vertical 'V' copper wire surface element.

Phase 1 (P1): **9 gauge wire (primary surface structure)**
Phase 2 (P2): **9 gauge wire (consequent volumetric connection)**
Phase 3 (P3): **Elastic string (single node)**
Phase 4 (P4): **Elastic string (volumetric node)**

[Test 2B Video](#)

Set Up: Two fixed linear elements with a 'V' surface structure.

P1: Surface node connection. The fixed linear element is bending under tension.

P2: Connecting surface elements on a translated horizontal axis.

P3: Elastic string top node loop 1; connecting surface and linear elements.

P3: Elastic string top node loop 2; constructing a knot using loops.

P3: Securing elastic top node connection by knotting 2 loops.

P4: Connecting elastic string to the second linear copper element.

P4: Looping elastic string over the translated linear element.

P5: Securing loops across both linear elements forming a volumetric structure.

9. PHYSICAL TEST 2: CONNECTION NODES (LOOPS)

Linear structures, surface structures and volumetric structures are connected at nodes. The node connection varies by material type and factors like friction, torsion capacity, tensile strength, elasticity need to be considered when analysing node-connections.

Image 6: Close-up shots for drone-woven

9. PHYSICAL TEST 2: CONNECTION NODES (LOOPS) ANALYSIS

9. UAV MOVEMENT Loop Formation

The drone creates **multiple loops to form a knot**. Diagram 16 shows how the drone would use **coordinates in a 3D plane** to create a knot. This will be primarily applicable when the UAV ties loops to dynamically weave **data nests in phase 3**.

It will also construct the **coordinate nodes**; the same **vector logic** is followed. **Different material properties** including ductility, malleability and tension will be programmed for in the **phase-wise UAV commands**.

2	3	4	5
0	0	1	0
+2	-3	+2	-1

Copper wire has better **shape-retaining properties** than thread so it would require lesser loops to form a knot. Additionally, copper wires can be **twisted to fix a node**. Diagram 16 shows possible types of loop and knot movements to create a fixed node.

Diagram 16: Vector coordinates for a single loop.

Hierarchy of nodes:

1. Single end fixed node:

a. Attaching **phase 1 elements** to existing architectural infrastructure.

Example: Looping one end of a copper wire to a **roof overhang**.

b. Attaching **phase 2 elements** to **pre-existing phase 1 nodes**.

2. Double end open node:

a. Weaving **phase 3 elements** using existing phase 1 and 2 infrastructure. This would require **creating a node on an existing wire** and thus require a **tauter knot** as the **tertiary wire will be tense** from opposing directions.

Diagram 17: Twisting copper wire

Parts of a Knot:

Diagram 18: Parts of a knot.

Bight

Any part of the tensile element between ends.

Crossing Point

The point where ends cross in making a loop.

Elbow

Two parts of a tensile elements in close contact with each other.

Loop

A bight becomes a loop when two sections of the tensile elements cross.

Standing End

The stagnant end not used to tie the knot.

The active end used to tie a knot.

9. TESTING WAYPOINT FOLLOWING ON MATLAB

This test simulates waypoint following to see how a **UAV path can be simulated by outlining specific points in its path**. The code creates a controller that helps a UAV follow points to create its path. The code is simulated in **Simulink**.

1. Guidance Model Configuration

The model assumes a fixed wing quadcopter on autopilot mode.

```
open_system('uavStepResponse');
```

2. Integration with Waypoint Follower

This module is used to assemble the control and environmental input for the guidance model block.

```
open_system('fixedWingPathFollowing');
```

3. Waypoint Follower Configuration

This step has three modules:

- a. **UAV Waypoint Follower** block:
Identifies the direction based on the heading position, lookahead distance and coordinate points.
- b. **UAV Heading Controller**
Controls the heading angle by regulating the roll angle.
- c. **UAV Animation**
Visualises the UAV Flight Path.

Image 8: Simulink modules.

4. Simulation

Simulating the model; the controller Waypoint Following can be adjusted using

Example 1:
Small Lookahead distance (5)
Fast Heading control (3.9)
Result:
Curvy path between waypoints.

Example 2:
Large Lookahead distance (49)
Slow Heading control (0.4)
Result:
More precise path on waypoints.

Diagram 19: Example 1 Simulation Result

Diagram 20: Example 2 Simulation Result

Each step shows the used module from MATLAB and Simulink's UAV Programming Toolbox. The Waypoint Following Module tested **how a drone can follow a selection of coordinates by modulating its heading control and lookahead distance**. The results show that a **large lookahead distance and slow heading control** creates a **more precise path**.

```
% close Simulink models
close_system("uavStepResponse");
close_system("fixedWingPathFollowing");
```

Static Object Avoidance is when a drone uses LiDAR (Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) to determine the distance from nearby objects and consequently change its path while still following the programmed trajectory. For the intervention, static object avoidance is important for two reasons:

1. Noticing existing building elements to create a path around them.
2. Detecting existing phase 1 and phase 2 and flying around them.

Create the scenario

```
# Create the scenario
Scenario = uavScenario("UpdateRate",100,"ReferenceLocation",[0 0 0]);
addMesh(Scenario,"cylinder",{[0 0 1] [0 .01]},{[0 1 0]});
```

Define the UAV platform

```
#Define the UAV platform
InitialPosition = [0 0 -7];
InitialOrientation = [0 0 0];
platUAV = uavPlatform("UAV",Scenario, ...
    "ReferenceFrame","NED", ...
    "InitialPosition",InitialPosition, ...
    "InitialOrientation",eul2quat(InitialOrientation));

updateMesh(platUAV,"quadrotor",{1.2},{[0 0 1],eul2tform([0 0 pi])});
```

Mount the LiDAR sensor module

```
#Mount the LiDAR sensor module
AzimuthResolution = 0.5;
ElevationResolution = 2;
MaxRange = 7;
AzimuthLimits = [-179 179];
ElevationLimits = [-15 15];
LidarModel = uavLidarPointCloudGenerator("UpdateRate",10, ...
    "MaxRange",MaxRange, ...
    "RangeAccuracy",3, ...
    "AzimuthResolution",AzimuthResolution, ...
    "ElevationResolution",ElevationResolution, ...
    "AzimuthLimits",AzimuthLimits, ...
    "ElevationLimits",ElevationLimits, ...
    "HasOrganizedOutput",true);
```

```
uavSensor("Lidar",platUAV,LidarModel, ...
    "MountingLocation",[0 0 -0.4], ...
    "MountingAngles",[0 0 180]);
```

Add obstacles to the scenario

```
#Add Obstacles to the scenario
ObstaclePositions = [10 0; 20 10; 10 20]; % Locations of the obstacles
ObstacleHeight = 15; % Height of the obstacles
ObstaclesWidth = 3; % Width of the obstacles

for i = 1:size(ObstaclePositions,1)
    addMesh(Scenario,"polygon", ...
        [ObstaclePositions(i,1)-ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)-ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
        ObstaclePositions(i,1)+ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)-ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
        ObstaclePositions(i,1)+ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)+ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
        ObstaclePositions(i,1)-ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)+ObstaclesWidth/2], ...
        [0 ObstacleHeight]),0.651*ones(1,3));
end
show3D(Scenario);
legend("Start Position","Obstacles")
```

Visualizing the created 3D scenario.

Visualizing created obstacles.

Simulink Model Overview

The Simulink model has 4 main components:

- 1. UAV Scenario:** Configures the context scenario and visualises the UAV's trajectory.
- 2. Waypoint following and obstacle avoidance:** Takes point cloud data and existing UAV state to calculate an


```
Waypoints = [InitialPosition; 0 20 -7; 20 20 -7; 20 0 -7];
for i = 2:size(Waypoints,1)
    addMesh(Scenario,"cylinder",{[Waypoints(i,2) Waypoints(i,1) 1] [0 0.1]},{[1 0 0]});
end
show3D(Scenario);
hold on
plot3([InitialPosition(1,2); Waypoints(:,2)], [InitialPosition(1,2); Waypoints(:,1)], [-InitialPosition(1,3); -Waypoints(:,3)], "-g")
legend(["Start Position","Obstacles","","","Waypoints","","","Direct Path"])
```
- 3. Controller and plant:** Updates the position of the UAV using control commands based on the distance from


```
# Proportional Gains
Px = 6;
Py = 6;
Pz = 6.5;
# Derivative Gains
Dx = 1.5;
Dy = 1.5;
Dz = 2.5;
# Integral Gains
Ix = 0;
Iy = 0;
Iz = 0;
# Filter Coefficients
Nx = 10;
Ny = 10;
Nz = 14.4947065605712;
UAVSampleTime = 0.001;
Gravity = 9.81;
DroneMass = 0.1;
```
- 4. Control panel:** Enables and dis-

Simulink modules.

Image sequence for iterative obstacle avoidance.

Simulating the model

```
out = sim("ObstacleAvoidanceDemo.slx");
```

Visualising the UAV trajectory

```
hold on
points = squeeze(out.trajectoryPoints(1,:,:));
plot3(points(:,2),points(:,1),-points(:,3)),"-r");
legend(["Start Position","Obstacles","","","Waypoints","","","Direct Path","UAV Trajectory"])
```

Video: Visualising the UAV trajectory.

Moving Object Avoidance is when a drone uses LiDAR (Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) to determine the distance from nearby moving objects, guessing the direction of the moving object and consequently change its path while still following the programmed path.

For the intervention, moving object avoidance is important for learning about the presence of humans and flying around them to avoid injuries.

Create the testing scenario:

```
# Create a scenario that runs for 10 seconds.
s = uavScenario("StopTime",30,"HistoryBufferSize",200);

# Create a fixed-wing target that moves from [30 0 0] to [20 10 0].
target = uavPlatform("Target",s,"Trajectory",waypointTrajectory([30 0 0; 0 30 0],"TimeOfArrival",[0 30]));
updateMesh(target,"fixedwing",{1},[1 0 0],eul2tform([0 0 pi]));

# Create a quadrotor as the ego vehicle.
egoVelocity = [1 1 0];
egoMultirotor = uavPlatform("EgoVehicle",s,"InitialVelocity", egoVelocity);
updateMesh(egoMultirotor,"quadrotor",{1},[0 1 0],eul2tform([0 0 pi]));

# Create a radar sensor and set up its properties.
radarSensor = radarDataGenerator("no_scanning","SensorIndex",1,"UpdateRate",10,...
    "FieldOfView",[120 80],...
    "HasElevation", true,...
    "ElevationResolution", 3,...
    "AzimuthResolution", 1, ...
    "RangeResolution", 10, ... meters
    "RangeRateResolution",3,...
    "RangeLimits", [0 750],...
    "TargetReportFormat","Tracks",...
    "TrackCoordinates",'Scenario',...
    "HasINS", true,...
    "HasFalseAlarms",true,...
    "FalseAlarmRate",1e-5,...
    "HasRangeRate",true,...
    "FalseAlarmRate", 1e-7);

# Mount the radar sensor on the ego vehicle.
radar = uavSensor("Radar",egoMultirotor,ExampleHelperUAVRadar(radarSensor),"MountingAngles", [0 0 0]);
```

The testing scenario has two UAVs:
UAV A: Mounted with a radar sensor
UAV B: Acts as the moving obstacle

UAV A detects and alters its path by detecting the velocity of UAV B.

Simulating the scenario without obstacle avoidance:

```
# This scenario shows how a moving UAV could collide with moving obstacles, such as humans.
# Set up the 3D view of the scenario.
[ax, plotFrames] = show3D(s);
# Represent the ego UAV as a green marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","green","Parent",plotFrames.EgoVehicle.BodyFrame);
# Represent the other UAV as a red marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","red","Parent",plotFrames.Target.BodyFrame);
xlim([-5,35]);
ylim([-5,35]);

# Start simulation.
setup(s);
while advance(s)
# Move ego UAV along its velocity vector.
motion = read(egoMultirotor);
motion(1:2) = motion(1:2) + motion(4:5)/s.UpdateRate;
move(egoMultirotor, motion);

show3D(s,"FastUpdate", true,"Parent",ax);
pause(0.02);
end
```

This scenario shows how a moving UAV could collide with moving obstacles, such as humans.

Configuring obstacle behaviour:

```
# Set up safety radius
radiusUAV = 0.5; % UAV radius (m)
radiusObs = 2; % Obstacle radius (m)
safetyDist = 2; % Collision safety radius (m) - same for all obstacles
effectiveRadius = radiusUAV+radiusObs+safetyDist;

# Time Horizon (time until collision to perform avoidance maneuver)
Th = 10; % sec
```

Potential collisions with moving objects are predicted by measuring

Simulating the scenario and testing obstacle avoidance:

```
# Set up the 3D view of the scenario.
[ax,plotFrames] = show3D(s);
# Represent the ego UAV as a green marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","green","Parent",plotFrames.EgoVehicle.BodyFrame);
# Represent the other UAV as a red marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","red","Parent",plotFrames.Target.BodyFrame);
xlim([-5,35]);
ylim([-5,35]);
# Start simulation.
restart(s);
setup(s);
desVel = egoVelocity(1:2);
while advance(s)
# Move the ego UAV along its velocity vector.
motion = read(egoMultirotor);
motion(1:2) = motion(1:2) + desVel/s.UpdateRate;
motion(4:5) = desVel;
move(egoMultirotor, motion);
# Update sensor readings and read data.
updateSensors(s);
# Obtain detections from the radar.
[isUpdated,time,confTracks,numTracks,config] = read(radar);
# Perform obstacle avoidance maneuver by adjusting ego vehicle's velocity
desVel = egoVelocity(1:2);
if numTracks > 0
# Detect imminent collision using
# exampleHelperDetectImminentCollision function.
obstacleStates = [confTracks.State];
[isOnCollisionPath,VOFrontAngle,VOBackAngle,VOMinAngle,VOMaxAngle] ...
= exampleHelperDetectImminentCollision(motion(1:2)', motion(4:5)', obstacleStates([1,3],:), ...
obstacleStates([2,4],:),effectiveRadius,Th);
# Find obstacles that are on imminent collision path.
collisionObsIdx = find(isOnCollisionPath);
if any(isOnCollisionPath)
# Compute the velocity required to avoid collision using the
# exampleHelperCVHeuristic2D function.
desVel = exampleHelperCVHeuristic2D(norm(egoVelocity), ...
motion(1:2)', ...
motion(4:5)', ...
obstacleStates([1,3],collisionObsIdx), ...
obstacleStates([2,4],collisionObsIdx), ...
effectiveRadius, ...
VOFrontAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
VOBackAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
VOMinAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
VOMaxAngle(collisionObsIdx), Th);
desVel = desVel';
end
end
show3D(s,"FastUpdate", true,"Parent",ax);
pause(0.02);
end
```

The obstacle avoidance algorithm attempts at finding and following a collision-free direction based on the velocity of the moving object.

Video: Colli-

Video: Avoid-

Testing obstacle avoidance for UAVs through MATLAB taught the logistics of how a UAV weaving a copper intervention can dynamically update its preprogrammed trajectory.

9.PHASE 0: IDENTIFYING ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENTS

An on-site study was conducted, in Canary Wharf, to identify **common street furniture** and **facade elements** that can be utilised as **latches for attaching hooks for phase 0 aluminium pipes**. Building-specific architectural elements for 25 Bank Street include:

- Hollow facade pipes
- Street overhangs
- CCTV casings
- Wall-mounted lamps

Common **street furniture** found in Canary Wharf includes:

- Lamp posts
- Traffic signals
- Planters
- Street signs

Street Signs

Appendix 1 shows site-images.

Phases 1, 2, 3 (page 69) have Different materials and attachments.

Phase 1: Hooks attached to **aluminium tubes** to connext primary architectural elements.

Phase 2 has **elastic hooks with special carabiner hooks** to attach to coordinate nodes and phase 1 elements.

Phase 3 has **galvanized copper wire** that can be looped (63) and knotted to create data nest connections from dynamic pedestrian traffic across the intervention's active period.

Planters

Facade street-side overhang and lamps.

9. PHASES 1, 2, 3: ATTACHMENT DETAILS

9. UAV MOVEMENT

Phase 1

Phase 3: Context-specific

Material: Galvanized Copper Wire.

Phase 2: Data-specific

Material: Elastic hook with special carabiner hooks.

Phase 1: Site-specific

Material: Aluminium tube wrapped around an elastic rope.

The elastic rope inside aluminium tubes allows slight flexibility about phase 1 site-specific connections.

Extended Phase 1 tube

Detail drawing:
Site-specific attachment hook

Examples: Phase 1 hook latching onto existing architectural elements (Ex. Traffic light, Facade pipes and streetside planters).

In order to attach **hooks for phase 1**, create **nodes for phase 2** and tie **knots for phase 3**, the UAV needs to work like fingers. This drawing outlines the **three attachments** designed to help the UAV conduct relevant movements. Each attachment helps replicate a finger movement (Clasping, pressing and holding).

Top Isometric

Right Elevation

9. UAV ATTACHMENT DETAILS

9. UAV MOVEMENT UAV Attachments

There are three attachments that aid UAV construction:

- A. **Grabber:** Releases and grabs the weighted Free End of the copper wire.
- B. **Presser:** Is fixed on the UAV base and is used to press parts of the knot.
- C. **Holder:** There are two holders, which hold and work the wires.

A. Grabber

The grabber replicated the action of closing and releasing a weight. The 'weight' can also be a hook (phase 1/2) or a loose end of a copper wire (phase 3).

It releases the weight and then spins around the architectural element to catch the weight again.

B. Presser

The Presser replicates the role for a thumb and **puts pressure onto one section..** It also **has grooves** that help hold the working end of the wire in a stagnant position to help the UAV tie the knot using the working end.

C. Holders

The third attachment is a **sliding system with two holders.** The holders are tweezer-like attachments that represent two fingers working with a thread.

The Holders can **move in two dimensions** across the sliding plate and also **move up and down in the third axis.** The holder head can be **rotated to twist the wire.**

10. ALGORITHM ITERATIONS

The power held by Financial monopolies in the Financial Markets can be **measured using their profits**. Financial Data for JP Morgan will directly inform the complexity and form of every intervention.

The **higher their profits**, the **more complex the intervention** will be, thus **spatialising the extent to which financial giants exploit their position of power** within financial markets.

This section outlines various algorithm iterations that were developed to try and efficiently **convert the quantitative data into a spatial intervention**, following data collection.

Note: *Algorithms 1 and 2 were developed keeping a 4 day, 23 hour weaving period in mind. These are the active hours when Foreign Exchange financial markets are active in London. The intervention was set to collapse after 4 days and 23 hours. However, the final REWIRE algorithm is a continuously growing structure that uses various data inputs and collapses at the end of the financial year.*

Image 11: Forex data representation on trading platforms.

10.2 ALGORITHM 1: DIRECT CONNECTION

Using market data for profit per financial quarter for the past 10 years:

From the three categories of data extracted, each column formed one axis.
Every row of data was converted into a single coordinate:

(x, y, z) = (year, % change, financial profits)

Every coordinate was placed into the 3D vector space.

Algorithm 1 creates the spatial intervention by connecting two consequent coordinates directly.

Example:

2013 (Quarter 1) = (1, -13, 11) is connected to 2013 (Quarter 2) = (2, -1, 12)

10. ALGORITHM ITERATIONS Algorithm 1 Method

Coordinates (x, y, z)	
(1,-13,11)	(21,-11,7)
(2,-1,12)	(22,-3,9)
(3,-16,12)	(23,-6,9)
(4,20,14)	(24,11,10)
(5,-9,12)	(25,-10,8)
(6,-8,12)	(26,3,9)
(7,-14,13)	(27,10,9)
(8,33,15)	(28,11,8)
(9,-2,11)	(29,-11,7)
(10,-48,12)	(30,-6,8)
(11,64,16)	(31,-9,9)
(12,5,10)	(32,22,10)
(13,1,9)	(33,-17,7)
(14,-3,9)	(34,-2,9)
(15,-2,10)	(35,4,9)
(16,26,10)	(36,28,9)
(17,-16,7)	(37,-22,6)
(18,-11,9)	(38,-17,8)
(19,-6,10)	(39,-3,10)
(20,30,10)	(40,0,10)

Table 8. Raw data converted to coordinates.

Example:

(1, -13, 11) = (2013 Quarter 1, -13% change in profits from the last quarter, \$11,000 Million profits)

Diagram 25: Isometric graph for iteration 1.

Diagram 26: Unfolded Plan, Side Elevation and Front Elevation for Algorithm 1.

Reflection:

Algorithm 1 was a good starting point but it didn't provide a **complex inhabitable space**. Further iterations can experiment with **alternative ways to connect the coordinates** derived from the data, instead of a straight connection.

Algorithm 2 was tested using a **physical model**. Algorithm 1 explored how data can be converted to coordinate points and how those coordinate points can be plotted in space to create an intervention. Algorithm 2 is **site-specific** and explores how data for any financial entity can be used to **create a woven copper intervention** on a subsequent physical site.

The algorithm has 4 phases:

0. Path Plotting: Site Scanning, identifying architectural elements and plotting the path.

1. Context Node Creation: Latching onto architectural elements using [name] knot and connecting nodes using primary tensile wire elements.

2. Triangulation: Connecting primary wire elements using secondary wire elements to form triangular planes.

3. Data-driven weaving: Projecting, plotting and connecting market data onto triangular surfaces.

Algorithm 2 was tested using the site for **JP Morgan:**
25 Bank Street, Canary Wharf, London, E14 5JP.

10.3A PHASE 0 : PATH PLOTTING

Phase 0 begins at sharp 22:00 GMT on Sunday, when the UAV emerges from the control box and starts scanning the site using LiDAR sensors (Section 8. Physical Context Integration).

Diagram 27. Representational elevation for 25 Bank Street.

The base is a massing model with architectural elements found on the site at street-level:

Plan

Front Elevation

Left Elevation

Right Elevation

10.3B PHASE 1 : MODEL OVERVIEW

Every intervention can have different sites. Phase 1 creates primary linear structural elements by connecting nodes from existing architectural structures (Section [x]: Title). The model simulates nodes by using screw hooks attached on elements. 1.5 mm thick copper wire is used to construct the primary linear elements.

Plan

Front Elevation

Left Elevation

Right Elevation

Diagram 28: Identified nodes for primary wire attachments.

■ Node on existing
■ architectural elements

10.3B PHASE 1 : MODEL DETAILS

Attachments mainly loop around the **base of lampposts or screw hooks**. Phase 1 connections are the **primary links to the physical context architecture**. After the active weaving period is over, **the quick-release knots will be released**, enabling the entire canopy to collapse.

10. ALGORITHM ITERATIONS
Algorithm 2 Phase 1:
Content Node Creation

Model Details: Nodes details and attaching to site-specific conditions through architectural ele-

Phase 1 Plan

Phase 1 Front Elevation

Phase 1 Isometric

Phase 1 Side Elevation

10.3C PHASE 2 : MODEL OVERVIEW

Phase 2 uses the linear elements from phase 1 and connects them to create **secondary surface structures**. Every phase 2 element is a **secondary linear node** that works towards weaving a **complete triangle** as one surface structure, using existing primary linear elements. **1 mm silver-plated copper wire** represents **secondary linear nodes** used to create triangles.

Plan

Front Elevation

Left Elevation

Right Elevation

10.3C PHASE 2 : MODEL DETAILS

Phase 2 connections loop around existing primary nodes and tensile wires from phase 1. The UAV uses a looping mechanism to create sturdy knots, not quick-release knots. Therefore all wire-connections for phase 2 are entirely dependent on the primary knot node connections from Phase 1. Secondary tensile elements created in phase 2 work towards connecting existing primary elements from phase 1 to create closed triangular planes.

Phase 2 connections require UAVs to loop around existing architectural elements. This includes looping around gaps on the base of planters, lamp post bases, unused lamp post branches [diagram 29], CCTV covers, lamps on the overhang, etc...

Working end: Connected to other primary nodes.

Working end:
Connected to other primary nodes.

Diagram 29: Detail for how a drone repeatedly loops around existing architectural elements to create closed triangular surfaces for Phase 2.

Phase 2 Plan

Phase 2 Front Elevation

Phase 2 Isometric

Phase 2 Side Elevation

10.3D PHASE 3 : OVERVIEW AND PROCESS

Phase 3 includes UAVs using **market data for each financial entity** to weave over the structural infrastructure created in phase 1 and phase 2. The algorithm used for phase 3 continues using market data, converted into coordinates but **utilises a different spatialization process** from algorithm 1.

Individual nodes from **Phase 2 create triangular surface structures**. Each side of a single triangular surface becomes one axis, corresponding to one coordinate from the data (Table 9). An **X-Y-Z plane** is projected onto every individual triangular surface (Diagram 31). Every side of the triangle gets **scaled and divided** according to the range of the data (Table 9).

For example, R corresponds to the 'Years' column, representing financial quarters. The data ranges from 1 to 40. In turn, every R axis on the intervention will have 40 divisions. As there are 40 data points, there will be 40 triangular surfaces. The divisions will be inputted as coordinates in a 3D space into the drone's path program (Diagram 30).

The drone then **projects each coordinate** and weaves from R_1 to G_1 to B_1 , finishing coordinate one. From B_2 it moves to R_1 line for the next triangular surface and weaves from R_1 to G_2 to B_2 .

Diagram 30. Each side of a single triangular surface becomes once axis. Every side is scaled according to the data range.

Diagram [x]: UAV path chronology

Diagram [x]: Front Elevation speculative descriptive view of triangular surfaces.

This motion is panned out over the duration of 4 days. As the **number of data points increases**, there are **more triangular surfaces**, thus **increasing the complexity** of the intervention.

Diagram 31: Isometric speculative descriptive view of triangular surfaces.

10. ALGORITHM ITERATIONS

Algorithm 2 Phase 3:
Overview

Years / Quarters	% Change	Revenue	Years / Quarters	% Change	Revenue
1	-13	11	21	-11	7
2	-1	12	22	-3	9
3	-16	12	23	-6	9
4	20	14	24	11	10
5	-9	12	25	-10	8
6	-8	12	26	3	9
7	-14	12	27	10	9
8	33	15	28	11	8
9	-2	11	29	-11	7
10	-48	12	30	-6	8
11	64	16	31	-9	9
12	5	10	32	22	10
13	1	9	33	-17	7
14	-3	9	34	-2	9
15	-2	10	35	4	9
16	26	10	36	28	9
17	-16	7	37	-22	6
18	-11	9	38	-17	8
19	-6	10	39	-3	10
20	30	10	40	0	10
Range:			[1, 40]	[-70, 50]	[0, 20]
Number of points:			40 points	21 points	121 points

Table 9. The range of every data set is used to scale individual sides for triangles.

10.3D PHASE 3 : ALGORITHM DETAIL DRAWINGS

These drawings are **diagrammatic representations** of how each triangular surface created in Phase 2 is read as **R, G, and B**. This information is used to **project and weave individual data points** onto the existing copper canopy.

RGB Lines Plan

RGB Lines Front Elevation

RGB Lines Isometric

10.3D PHASE 3 : MODEL OVERVIEW

The physical model uses a black polyester thread to overlay each coordinate onto one triangle. There are 40 triangles, representing 40 data points. In reality, this phase will take the longest time over the 4 day and 23 hour weaving period. It will also create the most street-level blockages as it will increase the density of the copper canopy significantly.

Plan

Front Elevation

Left Elevation

Right Elevation

10.3D PHASE 3 : MODEL DETAILS

Phase 3 connections work solely by looping onto existing primary and secondary tensile elements from phases 1 and 2. Therefore, all phase 3 wire elements are completely dependent on the pre-existing copper infrastructure woven by the UAV.

Model Details: Nodes details and attaching to site-specific conditions through architectural elements.

Phase 3 Plan

Phase 3 Front Elevation

Phase 3 Isometric

Phase 3 Side Elevation

10.3E ALGORITHM 2 : COPPER WIRE FORCES

The entire infrastructure is constructed using copper wires. Copper wires function purely in tension. At every node, the copper wire will exert a tension force which will be opposed by the solid element at the node; ex. an existing architectural elements such as a lamp post or another tensile wire (Diagrams 33 and 34).

Copper also bends, so if there are two or more wires at a node, they will flexibly readjust till the node is in equilibrium with the opposing tension force acting against the direction of all copper wires.

Diagram 32. Tension forces at nodes.

Tension forces increase with length, so wires connecting nodes that are farther apart will have higher tension than wires that connect nodes within a shorter distance.

Diagram 33: Looping around a lamp post base

Diagram 34: Looping around an existing wire

The added tension causes the primary wire to bend but the tension forces oppose each other to bring the system to equilibrium.

However, the research does not test the tensile limit of copper. Copper has the potential to snap if its tensile limit is exceeded by additional load. Loads on the copper infrastructure are mainly natural loads, ex. wind, however every human interaction exerts a load too. With every additional human load, the tensile force momentarily increases. Therefore, tensile wires that are at street level need to be connected across nodes with multiple wires. Street-level tensile wires will have the most human interaction and therefore will need the ability to resist the highest loads. Having multiple wires will help distribute the load to prevent the copper wires from exceeding their tensile limit and snapping.

Another additional load is the increasing weight of the intervention itself. As the 4 day, 23 hour weaving period progresses, the intervention grows in weight. Therefore, there should be a sufficient amount of nodes to distribute the increasing load. Phase 2 of the algorithm creates additional nodes to complete triangles. Phase 3 adds the highest weight of additional copper wire but does not create additional nodes and instead weaves onto existing infrastructure. Therefore, the weaving needs to span across the intervention (Diagram 35) over each phase 3 connection to ensure that no single section collapses due to exceeding load.

Diagram 35: A visual representation of phase 3 weaving spanning across the span of the site to avoid collapse of single sections due to exceeding load.

10.3F ALGORITHM 2 : SUMMARY

Plan

Front Elevation

Isometric

Phase 1: Context Node Cre-

Phase 2: Triangulation

Phase 3: Data-driven

Side Elevation

Section AA'

Phase

Time

0

Day 1: 22:00 GMT Sunday to 22:00 GMT Monday

1

Day 2:
22:00 GMT Monday to 22:00 GMT Tuesday

2

Day 3:
22:00 GMT Tuesday to 22:00 GMT Wednesday

3

Day 3 and 4:
22:00 GMT Wednesday to 21:00 GMT Friday.

[collapse]

Reflection

Upon looking at the drawing compilations, Algorithm 2 **successfully translates stock market revenue data into an interesting spatial intervention**. There is a great proportionality relationship between translating revenue data and the complexity of the intervention. Moving forward, I would like to explore logistics of what happens after the **intervention collapses** after the 4 day and 23 hour weaving period, and how the collapsed copper infrastructure can be **utilised as a platform for protest**.

SUMMARY

In conclusion, this project book introduces **REWIRE**: an architectural protest uniting **architecture, data, and political activism** to challenge banks and empower day traders. It delves into its genesis, from the context of day trading to a **double-sided investment pitch** and the significance of JP Morgan's **25 Bank Street** sample site.

The **REWIRE Algorithm** is the core of the project. The research showcases its phases, technical intricacies, and engagement elements. The **physical architectural intervention** is explored, with elevations, plans, visualizations, and model images that capture its essence.

The **protest phase** reveals the **acquisition process**, where participants symbolically reclaim unethical practices. This leads to the final '**Architectural Collapse**', strategically timed to create negative publicity and ignite a **larger protest against large financial entities**.

The role of **Unmanned Aerial Vehicles** (UAVs) is examined, along with the evolution of algorithm iterations, and additional context provided in the appendix.

This research book relays through REWIRE's attempt at **transcending traditional power systems** and forging a more equitable future through an **architectural, data-driven protest**.

11. APPENDICES:

Appendix 1: **Financialisation and Art**

Appendix 2: **MATLAB Tests**

Appendix 3: **Canary Wharf Site Images**

Appendix 4: **Arduino Tests: Data Visualization**

MATLAB tests were used to simulate UAV behaviour.

This test simulates waypoint following to see how a UAV path can be simulated by outlining specific points in its path. The code creates a controller that helps a UAV follow points to create its path. The code is simulated in Simulink.

1. Guidance Model Configuration

The model assumes a fixed wing quadcopter on autopilot mode.

2. Integration with Waypoint Follower

This module is used to assemble the control and environmental input for the guidance model block.

3. Waypoint Follower Configuration

This step has three modules:

a. **UAV Waypoint Follower** block:
Identifies the direction based on the heading position, lookahead distance and coordinate points.

b. **UAV Heading Controller**
Controls the heading angle by regulating the roll angle.

c. **UAV Animation**
Visualises the UAV Flight Path.

Image 8: Simulink modules.

4. Simulation

Simulating the model; the controller Waypoint Following can be adjusted using sliders:

Example 1:
Small Lookahead distance (5)
Fast Heading control (3.9)

Result:
Curvy path between waypoints.

Example 2:
Large Lookahead distance (49)
Slow Heading control (0.4)

Result:
More precise path on waypoints.

Diagram 19: Example 1 Simulation Result

Diagram 20: Example 2 Simulation Result

Each step shows the used module from MATLAB and Simulink's UAV Programming Toolbox. The Waypoint Following Module tested how a drone can follow a selection of coordinates by modulating its heading control and lookahead distance. The results show that a large lookahead distance and slow heading control creates a more precise path.

```
% close Simulink models
close_system("uavStepResponse");
close_system("fixedWingPathFollowing");
```

11.1B MATLAB: TESTING STATIC OBSTACLE AVOIDANCE

Static Object Avoidance is when a drone uses **LiDAR** (Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) to determine the distance from nearby objects and consequently **change its path while still following the programmed trajectory**.

For the intervention, static object avoidance is important for two reasons:

1. Noticing **existing building elements** to create a path around them.
2. Detecting **existing copper wires** and flying around them.

Create the scenario

```
Scenario = uavScenario("UpdateRate",100,"ReferenceLocation",[0 0 0]);
addMesh(Scenario,"cylinder",{[0 0 1] [0 .01]],[0 1 0]);
```

Define the UAV platform

```
InitialPosition = [0 0 -7];
InitialOrientation = [0 0 0];
platUAV = uavPlatform("UAV",Scenario, ...
    "ReferenceFrame","NED", ...
    "InitialPosition",InitialPosition, ...
    "InitialOrientation",eul2quat(InitialOrientation));

updateMesh(platUAV,"quadrotor",{1.2},[0 0 1],eul2tform([0 0 pi]));
```

Mount the LiDAR sensor module

```
AzimuthResolution = 0.5;
ElevationResolution = 2;
MaxRange = 7;
AzimuthLimits = [-179 179];
ElevationLimits = [-15 15];
LidarModel = uavLidarPointCloudGenerator("UpdateRate",10, ...
    "MaxRange",MaxRange, ...
    "RangeAccuracy",3, ...
    "AzimuthResolution",AzimuthResolution, ...
    "ElevationResolution",ElevationResolution, ...
    "AzimuthLimits",AzimuthLimits, ...
    "ElevationLimits",ElevationLimits, ...
    "HasOrganizedOutput",true);
```

```
uavSensor("Lidar",platUAV,LidarModel, ...
    "MountingLocation",[0 0 -0.4], ...
    "MountingAngles",[0 0 180]);
show3D(Scenario);
```

Add obstacles to the scenario

```
ObstaclePositions = [10 0; 20 10; 10 20]; % Locations of the obstacles
ObstacleHeight = 15; % Height of the obstacles
ObstaclesWidth = 3; % Width of the obstacles

for i = 1:size(ObstaclePositions,1)
    addMesh(Scenario,"polygon", ...
        {[ObstaclePositions(i,1)-ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)-ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
          ObstaclePositions(i,1)+ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)-ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
          ObstaclePositions(i,1)+ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)+ObstaclesWidth/2; ...
          ObstaclePositions(i,1)-ObstaclesWidth/2 ObstaclePositions(i,2)+ObstaclesWidth/2], ...
         [0 ObstacleHeight]},0.651*ones(1,3));
end
show3D(Scenario);
legend("Start Position","Obstacles")
```

Visualizing the created 3D scenario.

Visualizing created obstacles.

Simulink Model Overview

The Simulink model has 4 main components:

1. **UAV Scenario:** Configures the context scenario and visualises the UAV's trajectory.
2. **Waypoint following and obstacle avoidance:** Takes point cloud data and existing UAV state to calculate an


```
Waypoints = [InitialPosition; 0 20 -7; 20 20 -7; 20 0 -7];
for i = 2:size(Waypoints,1)
    addMesh(Scenario,"cylinder",{Waypoints(i,2) Waypoints(i,1) 1} [0 0.1],[1 0 0]);
end
show3D(Scenario);
hold on
plot3([InitialPosition(1,2); Waypoints(:,2)], [InitialPosition(1,2); Waypoints(:,1)], [-InitialPosition(1,3); -Waypoints(:,3)], "-g")
legend(["Start Position","Obstacles","","","Waypoints","","","Direct Path"])
```
3. **Controller and plant:** Updates the position of the UAV using control commands based on the distance from


```
# Proportional Gains
Px = 6;
Py = 6;
Pz = 6.5;
# Derivative Gains
Dx = 1.5;
Dy = 1.5;
Dz = 2.5;
# Integral Gains
Ix = 0;
Iy = 0;
Iz = 0;
# Filter Coefficients
Nx = 10;
Ny = 10;
Nz = 14.4947065605712;
UAVSampleTime = 0.001;
Gravity = 9.81;
DroneMass = 0.1;
```
4. **Control panel:** Enables and dis-

Simulink modules.

Image sequence for iterative obstacle avoidance.

Simulating the model

```
out = sim("ObstacleAvoidanceDemo.slx");
```

Visualising the UAV trajectory

```
hold on
points = squeeze(out.trajectoryPoints(1,:,:));
plot3(points(:,2),points(:,1),-points(:,3)),"-r");
legend(["Start Position","Obstacles","","","Waypoints","","","Direct Path","UAV Trajectory"])
```

[Video:](#) Visualising the UAV trajectory.

Moving Object Avoidance is when a drone uses LiDAR (Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) to determine the distance from nearby moving objects, guessing the direction of the moving object and consequently change its path while still following the programmed path.

Create the testing scenario:

```
# Create a scenario that runs for 10 seconds.
s = uavScenario("StopTime",30,"HistoryBufferSize",200);

# Create a fixed-wing target that moves from [30 0 0] to [20 10 0].
target = uavPlatform("Target",s,"Trajectory",waypointTrajectory([30 0 0; 0 30 0],"TimeOfArrival",[0 30]));
updateMesh(target,"fixedwing",{1},[1 0 0],eul2tform([0 0 pi]));

# Create a quadrotor as the ego vehicle.
egoVelocity = [1 1 0];
egoMultirotor = uavPlatform("EgoVehicle",s,"InitialVelocity", egoVelocity);
updateMesh(egoMultirotor,"quadrotor",{1},[0 1 0],eul2tform([0 0 pi]));

# Create a radar sensor and set up its properties.
radarSensor = radarDataGenerator("no_scanning","SensorIndex",1,"UpdateRate",10,...
    "FieldOfView",[120 80],...
    "HasElevation", true,...
    "ElevationResolution", 3,...
    "AzimuthResolution", 1, ...
    "RangeResolution", 10, ... meters
    "RangeRateResolution",3,...
    "RangeLimits", [0 750],...
    "TargetReportFormat","Tracks",...
    "TrackCoordinates",'Scenario',...
    "HasINS", true,...
    "HasFalseAlarms",true,...
    "FalseAlarmRate",1e-5,...
    "HasRangeRate",true,...
    "FalseAlarmRate", 1e-7);

# Mount the radar sensor on the ego vehicle.
radar = uavSensor("Radar",egoMultirotor,ExampleHelperUAVRadar(radarSensor),"MountingAngles", [0 0 0]);
```

Simulating the scenario without obstacle avoidance:

```
# This scenario shows how a moving UAV could collide with moving obstacles, such as humans.
# Set up the 3D view of the scenario.
[ax, plotFrames] = show3D(s);
# Represent the ego UAV as a green marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","green","Parent",plotFrames.EgoVehicle.BodyFrame);
# Represent the other UAV as a red marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","red","Parent",plotFrames.Target.BodyFrame);
xlim([-5,35]);
ylim([-5,35]);

# Start simulation.
setup(s);
while advance(s)
    # Move ego UAV along its velocity vector.
    motion = read(egoMultirotor);
    motion(1:2) = motion(1:2) + motion(4:5)/s.UpdateRate;
    move(egoMultirotor, motion);

    show3D(s,"FastUpdate", true,"Parent",ax);
    pause(0.02);
end
```

Configuring obstacle behaviour:

```
# Set up safety radius
radiusUAV = 0.5; % UAV radius (m)
radiusObs = 2; % Obstacle radius (m)
safetyDist = 2; % Collision safety radius (m) - same for all obstacles
effectiveRadius = radiusUAV+radiusObs+safetyDist;

# Time Horizon (time until collision to perform avoidance maneuver)
Th = 10; % sec
```

Simulating the scenario and testing obstacle avoidance:

```
# Set up the 3D view of the scenario.
[ax,plotFrames] = show3D(s);
# Represent the ego UAV as a green marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","green","Parent",plotFrames.EgoVehicle.BodyFrame);
# Represent the other UAV as a red marker.
plot3(0,0,0,"Marker","diamond","MarkerFaceColor","red","Parent",plotFrames.Target.BodyFrame);
xlim([-5,35]);
ylim([-5,35]);
# Start simulation.
restart(s);
setup(s);
desVel = egoVelocity(1:2);
while advance(s)
    # Move the ego UAV along its velocity vector.
    motion = read(egoMultirotor);
    motion(1:2) = motion(1:2) + desVel/s.UpdateRate;
    motion(4:5) = desVel;
    move(egoMultirotor, motion);
    # Update sensor readings and read data.
    updateSensors(s);
    # Obtain detections from the radar.
    [isUpdated,time,confTracks,numTracks,config] = read(radar);
    # Perform obstacle avoidance maneuver by adjusting ego vehicle's velocity
    desVel = egoVelocity(1:2);
    if numTracks > 0
        # Detect imminent collision using
        # exampleHelperDetectImminentCollision function.
        obstacleStates = [confTracks.State];
        [isOnCollisionPath,VOFrontAngle,VOBackAngle,VOMinAngle,VOMaxAngle] ...
        = exampleHelperDetectImminentCollision(motion(1:2)', motion(4:5)', obstacleStates([1,3],:), ...
        obstacleStates([2,4],:),effectiveRadius,Th);
        # Find obstacles that are on imminent collision path.
        collisionObsIdx = find(isOnCollisionPath);
        if any(isOnCollisionPath)
            # Compute the velocity required to avoid collision using the
            # exampleHelperCVHeuristic2D function.
            desVel = exampleHelperCVHeuristic2D(norm(egoVelocity), ...
            motion(1:2)', ...
            motion(4:5)', ...
            obstacleStates([1,3],collisionObsIdx), ...
            obstacleStates([2,4],collisionObsIdx), ...
            effectiveRadius, ...
            VOFrontAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
            VOBackAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
            VOMinAngle(collisionObsIdx), ...
            VOMaxAngle(collisionObsIdx), Th);
            desVel = desVel';
        end
    end
    show3D(s,"FastUpdate", true,"Parent",ax);
    pause(0.02);
end
```

For the intervention, moving object avoidance is mainly important for Learning about the **presence of humans** and flying around them to avoid injuries.

The testing scenario has two UAVs:
UAV A: **Mounted with a radar sensor**
UAV B: **Acts as the moving obstacle**

A detects and alters its path by detecting the velocity of B.

This scenario shows how a moving UAV could collide with moving

Potential collisions with moving objects are predicted by measuring

The obstacle avoidance algorithm attempts at finding and following a collision-free direction based on the velocity of the moving object.

Video: Colli-

Video: Avoid-

Testing obstacle avoidance for UAVs through MATLAB taught the logistics of

Facade views

Street-side walkway views

Street-level views

Lamp posts

Facade pipes

Planters

Day Trading

noun// buying or selling of a security in a single trading day, aiming to make profits over short-term investments.

Types of securities:

- Stocks
- Cryptocurrencies
- Commodities
- Forex
- Binary Options
- Futures

Goal:

- Capitalise on small price movements of volatile stocks.
- In short periods of time (30 seconds, 1 minute, 5 minutes, etc...) stock values alter continuously with varying margins.

Most day-traders use platforms that show a list of securities available to trade, and also provide charts and patterns to help analyse trends.

Daytrading Platform [Left to right]: List of securities, selling and buying price, trend-chart for selected security, [bottom] traders' live orders. , [top-right]: total account balance.

11.3B DAY TRADING PLATFORMS

Since traders capitalise from short-term movements, they often track charts very closely, from 1-second changes over a day to 1-minute changes over 5 minutes.

SELL	BUY	Interval	History
1,242.16	1,242.96	1 second ★	Today ★
1,879.34 ▼	1,880.34	5 seconds ★	1 Day ★
2,572.10	2,574.40	10 seconds ★	3 Days ★
12,02... ▲	12,02...	30 seconds ★	1 Week ★
1.08577	1.09277	1 minute ★	1 Month ★
0.58408 ▲	0.58857	2 minutes ★	3 Months ★
0.25245	0.25436	3 minutes ★	6 Months ★
0.076...	0.077...	5 minutes ★	Year to date ★
87.824	87.904	10 minutes ★	1 Year ★
88.443	88.593	15 minutes ★	2 Years ★
417.20	420.97	30 minutes ★	5 Years ★
0.700	0.730	1 hour ★	Maximum ★
4.010	4.040	2 hours ★	
0.1680	0.1850	3 hours ★	
1.080	1.150	4 hours ★	
5.500	5.660	1 Day ★	
14.050	15.300	1 Week ★	
In Live Account only		1 Month ★	
102.738	102.753		
148.925	148.975		
981.81	982.63		
986.54	987.04		

UK-Natural Gas stock movement showing changes every 10-seconds in the last 51 minutes.

Daytrading Platform [Left to right]: Selling and buying prices, possible time-intervals to track a single-stock movement, history of time over which a stock's movement can be seen.

I chose day-trading because it is an act that became domestic and deals with data-changes over time in very precise intervals. The concept of time-precision was derived from the previous OBJECT exercise.

11.3C “HOW LONG DOES IT TAKE YOU TO MAKE YOUR FIRST TRADE?”

Trading platforms provide an overwhelming amount of data. Experienced traders are capable of analysing the data for their trades.

However, the information woverload works counter intuitively for first-time traders and often leads to a lack of confidence.

The graph shows responses from 25 traders from a survey, providing data on how long it took them to make their first trade.

Average time before making a first trade: 18.8 months.

Volatility

noun// Liability to change rapidly and unpredictably.

Volatility [in Finance]

noun// A statistical measure of the dispersion of returns for a given security or market index.

When the stock market rises or falls more than 1% in a single day, it is considered volatile.

Volatility can also be calculated for a single stock.

When the volatility is high, the stock price is changing (+ve and -ve) rapidly and steeply.

Price volatility for a single stock is important for day traders as it associates directly with risk because the price changes are less predictable.

Day traders capitalize from short-term volatility; the more volatile a stock, the more accurately they need to target their buying and selling time.

Higher Volatility

Higher chances for a larger profit [or loss].

Higher Risk

Calculating Volatility:

Volatility is calculated using variance and standard deviation of the stock prices.

$$vol = \sigma\sqrt{T}$$

vol = volatility over a given time period

= standard deviation of returns

T = number of periods in the time horizon

Factors affecting Volatility:

1. Interest rate hikes
2. Changes in other markets
3. Global Events
4. Monetary policies
5. Unexpected business decisions
6. Business instability

AIM: To test how photo-resistors work by connecting them to LEDs. Based on the light-intensity captures, different LED combinations will light-up.

COMPONENTS:

- 1 x Arduino Board
- 1 x Breadboard
- 9 x M-M wires
- 3 x 1K Resistors
- 2 x LEDs
- 1 x Photo-resistor

COMPONENT EXPLANATION:

Arduino Board: Arduino UNO board is a micro-controller, programmed by the IDE software on the computer.

Breadboard: Breadboards are used to create temporary circuits. It enables components to be inserted and removed with ease.

M-M jumper cables: Male-male jumper cables are used to internally connect components on a breadboard without the need for soldering.

Resistor: Resistors are passive devices that regulate the flow of electrical current in the entire circuit. The 1K resistor enables a resistance of 1K Ohms.

LED: An LED, Light-emitting-diode, is a semiconductor component that emits light when current passes through it.

Photo-resistor: Photo-resistors are sensors that change resistance based on the light-intensity they sense. With higher intensity, it will have a lower resistance and with lower intensity, it will have a higher resistance.

Electrical component CAD Drawing

Electrical component visual diagram

```

1  int light = 0; // store the current light value
2
3  void setup() {
4      // put your setup code here, to run once:
5      Serial.begin(9600); //configure serial to talk to computer
6      pinMode(13, OUTPUT); // configure digital pin 13 as an output
7      pinMode(12, OUTPUT); // configure digital pin 12 as an output
8  }
9
10 void loop() {
11     // put your main code here, to run repeatedly:
12     light = analogRead(A0); // read and save value from PR
13
14     Serial.println(light); // print current light value
15
16     if(light > 450) { // If it is bright...
17         Serial.println("It is quite light!");
18         digitalWrite(13,LOW); //turn left LED off
19         digitalWrite(12,LOW); // turn right LED off
20     }
21     else if(light > 229 && light < 451) { // If it is average light...
22         Serial.println("It is average light!");
23         digitalWrite(13, HIGH); // turn left LED on
24         digitalWrite(12,LOW); // turn right LED off
25     }
26     else { // If it's dark...
27         Serial.println("It is pretty dark!");
28         digitalWrite(13,HIGH); // Turn left LED on
29         digitalWrite(12,HIGH); // Turn right LED on
30     }
31     delay(1000); // don't spam the computer!
32 }

```

Arduino IDE code

Input: Varying light intensities

Output:

- If intensity > 450: Both LEDs off, printed 'It is quite light!'
- If 229 > intensity < 450: One LED on, printed 'It is average light!'
- In intensity < 229: Both LEDs on, printed 'It is pretty dark!'

The intensity values are derived after calibrating the light sensor. Calibration includes taking readings of light-intensities captured by the photoresistor without attaching any electrical components. The lowest intensity reading and highest intensity reading form the range, between which the threshold values dividing possible outputs are chosen.

Conclusion:

This test informed my understanding of how photoresistors behave as sensors. As a component, photoresistors will be now used for more complicated circuits.

AIM: Testing how manual input can lead to an output.

COMPONENTS:

- 1 x Arduino Board
- 1 x Breadboard
- 8 x M-M wires
- 1 x 1K Resistors
- 1 x LEDs
- 2 x Pushbuttons

COMPONENT EXPLANATION:

Push Button: Pushbuttons act as switches that connect two components across the circuit. The components connected for Test 2 are the LEDs and Power source.

Electrical component CAD Drawing

Electrical component visual diagram

```

1 // constants won't change. They're used here to set pin numbers:
2 const int buttonPin = 2; // the number of the pushbutton pin
3 const int ledPin = 13; // the number of the LED pin
4
5 // variables will change:
6 int buttonState = 0; // variable for reading the pushbutton status
7
8 void setup() {
9 // initialize the LED pin as an output:
10 pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT);
11 // initialize the pushbutton pin as an input:
12 pinMode(buttonPin, INPUT);
13 }
14
15 void loop() {
16 // read the state of the pushbutton value:
17 buttonState = digitalRead(buttonPin);
18
19 // check if the pushbutton is pressed. If it is, the buttonState is HIGH:
20 if (buttonState == HIGH) {
21 // turn LED on:
22 digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH);
23 } else {
24 // turn LED off:
25 digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW);
26 }
27 }
28
29

```

Arduino IDE code

Input: On/off input from the button. If the button is pressed once, the state is 'ON', if it is pressed again, the state is 'OFF'.

Output:

When the input changes from 'OFF' to 'ON', the LED glows red as current passes through it.

When the input changes from 'ON' to 'OFF', the LED stops glowing.

Conclusion:

This test was conducted to check how human mechanical inputs can affect outputs. Test 1 looked at an input-output sequence where the input was variable, changing with the environment, rather than mechanical.

Further tests will look into combining mechanical and un-controllable inputs. Architecturally, pushbuttons can be utilised to enable human movement as inputs into a circuit at the scale of an inhabitable space.

AIM: Testing a servo motor as a singular output.

COMPONENTS:

- 1 x Arduino Board
- 1 x Breadboard
- 3 x M-M wires
- 1 x Micro Servo motor

COMPONENT EXPLANATION:

Servo Motor: Servo motors have an electric motor, potentiometer (device used for measuring unknown voltage), a gearbox and control electronics. The output shaft is normally the gearbox connected to the motor. The position of the output shaft is measured by the potentiometer and compared with the target position outlined in the Arduino IDE code. The error is the difference between these two values, and is expressed through the actual movement of the output shaft. The servo motor moves between a range of 0 ° and 180 °.

Electrical component visual diagram

Electrical component CAD Drawing

```

1  #include <Servo.h>
2
3  Servo myservo; // 'myservo' is the object created for the motor, it will be referenced throughout.
4
5  void setup(){
6    myservo.attach(9); // connect pin 9 with the control line (the middle line of Servo)
7    myservo.write(90); // move servos to center position -> 90°
8  }
9  void loop(){
10   myservo.write(180); // move servos to center position -> 90°
11   delay(1000);
12   myservo.write(60); // move servos to center position -> 60°
13   delay(1000);
14   myservo.write(90); // move servos to center position -> 90°
15   delay(1000);
16   myservo.write(150); // move servos to center position -> 120°
17   delay(1000);
18 }
    
```

Arduino IDE code

Input: Digital pre-programmed directions from IDE.

Output: The motor moves with varying angles with a delay of 1000 microseconds (ms) between each movement. This is set up in a loop, so the motor will move continuously with 1000 ms pauses.

Conclusion: The primary purpose of this simple test was to understand microservo motor movement. Comprehending the 0 ° and 180 ° rotational range helps inform further tests that can be done using a micro servo as an output. Different motor-attachments to the gear shaft will also alter the output.

AIM: Experimenting with using proximity as an input for conducting mechanical work output through the motor.

COMPONENTS:

- 1 x Arduino Board
- 1 x Breadboard
- 9 x M-M wires
- 1 x Micro Servo motor
- 1 x Ultrasonic Distance sensor

COMPONENT EXPLANATION:

Ultrasonic Distance sensor: Ultrasonic sensors measure distance by emitting an ultrasound at a frequency of 40kHz. Ultrasound is a mechanical wave that travels through air. If there is an object in its path, the wave travels back to the sensor. The distance between the object and sensor is calculated by multiplying the travel time for the sensor to sense the wave and the speed of sound (343 m/s) and dividing it by two.

The formula is divided by two because this distance value provides the total distance for the wave to reach the object and travel back. The distance values can then be used to modulate outputs.

The ultrasonic sensor has four ports:

1. **VCC:** Power source; attaches to the +5V power supply.
2. **GND:** Attaches to the ground supply.
3. **Trig:** Trigger pin; outputs ultrasonic waves.
4. **Echo:** Input pin; receives ultrasonic waves, and outputs time (in ms).

Electrical component visual diagram

Ultrasonic sensor timing diagram

Line 4 of the code sets the trigger pin at a high state of 10 μs.

This will release eight 40 KHz cycle sonic waves that will travel at the speed of sound to the object, bounce back and be received at the Echo pin.

Ultrasonic wave transmission and reflection

Example calculation:

If the time taken for the wave to reflect back is 588 μs:

Speed of sound:
 $v = 343 \text{ m/s}$
 $v = 0.034 \text{ cm/}\mu\text{s}$

Time = 588 μs

Total Distance = Speed x Time
 $= 0.034 * 588 \approx 20 \text{ cm}$

Object Distance = (Total Distance)/2
 $= 20/2 = 10 \text{ cm}$

```

1  #include<Servo.h>
2  int trig=8;
3  int echo=9;
4  int dt=10;
5  Servo servo;
6
7  //int distance,duration;
8  void setup() {
9  | // put your setup code here, to run once:
10 pinMode(trig,OUTPUT);
11 pinMode(echo,INPUT);
12 Serial.begin(9600);
13 servo.attach(11);
14 }
15
16 void loop() {
17 | // put your main code here, to run repeatedly:
18
19
20 if (calc_dis(<10)
21 {
22   for (int i=0;i<=540;i++)
23   {
24     servo.write(i);
25     delay(1);
26   }
27   delay(100);
28   for (int i=540;i>=0;i--)
29   {
30     servo.write(i);
31     delay(1);
32   }
33   delay(100);
34 }
35 }
36
37 //Calculating distance using the ultrasonic sensor.
38
39 int calc_dis()
40 {
41   int duration,distance;
42   digitalWrite(trig,HIGH);
43   delay(dt);
44   digitalWrite(trig,LOW);
45   duration=pulseIn(echo,HIGH);
46   distance = (duration/2) / 29.1;
47   return distance;
48 }

```

Arduino IDE code

Electrical component CAD Drawing

Input: Ultrasonic sensor distance readings

Output:

Servo motor movement between 0° and 180 ° based on distance readings.

The motor is moved by a rotation angle of the distance recorded by the ultrasonic sensor.

Ex. If an object is 150 cm away from the sensor, the motor will move 150°.

Test 4 was conducted because using a variable distance input is a stable source of dynamic data. Using only photo-resistors may not generate enough dynamic and sensitive data to simulate stock-market volatility.

Conclusion:

This test enabled a connection between dynamic data and a subsequent constant output reflecting the data input.

The next Arduino test utilised ultrasonic sensor as one source of dynamic data and an alternative source of non-continuous data to have a wider dataset informing the singular motor output. Having a wider input dataset will enable the tests to replicate stock-market volatility.

AIM: Testing photoresistors as non-continuous inputs, ultrasonic sensors as a continuous input and a servo motor as a single output.

COMPONENTS:

- 1 x Arduino Board
- 1 x Breadboard
- 19 x M-M wires
- 2 x Micro Servo motor
- 3 x 1k Resistors
- 1 x Ultrasonic Distance sensor

Electrical component visual diagram

Electrical component CAD Drawing

The photoresistor input is connected to both servo motor 1 and servo motor 2, and the two LEDs. The ultrasonic sensor input is connected to servo motor 2.

Based on light intensity, the LEDs provide light outputs in the same combination as Test 1. The light intensity also moves motor 1 and motor 2.

Distance information from the ultrasonic sensor only inputs motor 2 and reflects readings on the serial monitor.

Therefore, motor 2 is the single output motor that can be used to visualise light and distance data inputs.

Showing numeric values for both light and distance input readings on the serial monitor allows for an alternative quantitative data-analysis, thus allowing for more options to visualise the complexity of volatile data.

```

1  #include <Servo.h>
2  int light = 0; // store the current light value
3  Servo s;
4
5  // constants for the ultrasonic sensor
6  const int TRIG_PIN = 6; // Arduino pin connected to Ultrasonic Sensor's TRIG pin
7  const int ECHO_PIN = 7; // Arduino pin connected to Ultrasonic Sensor's ECHO pin
8  const int SERVO_PIN = 10; // Arduino pin connected to Servo Motor's pin
9  const int DISTANCE_THRESHOLD = 10; // centimeters
10 Servo s2; // create servo object to control a servo
11
12 // variables for ultrasonic sensor
13 float duration_us, distance_cm;
14
15 void setup() {
16     // put your setup code here, to run once:
17     Serial.begin(9600); //configure serial to talk to computer
18     pinMode(4, OUTPUT); // configure digital pin 4 as an output
19     pinMode(2, OUTPUT); // configure digital pin 2 as an output
20     s.attach(11);
21
22     //Setup for the servo motor:
23     pinMode(TRIG_PIN, OUTPUT); // set arduino pin to output mode
24     pinMode(ECHO_PIN, INPUT); // set arduino pin to input mode
25     s2.attach(SERVO_PIN); // attaches the servo on pin 11 to the servo object
26     s2.write(0);
27 }
28
29 void loop() {
30     // put your main code here, to run repeatedly:
31     light = analogRead(A0); // read and save value from PR
32
33     Serial.println(light); // print current light value
34
35     if(light > 400) { // If it is bright...
36         Serial.println("It is quite light!");
37         digitalWrite(4,LOW); //turn left LED off
38         digitalWrite(2,LOW); // turn right LED off
39         s.write(180); // turn the motor 180 degrees
40     }
41
42     else if(light > 300 && light < 400) { // If it is average light...
43         Serial.println("It is average light!");
44         digitalWrite(4, HIGH); // turn left LED on
45         digitalWrite(2,LOW); // turn right LED off
46         s.write(90); // turn the motor 90 degrees
47     }
48
49     else if(light > 200 && light < 300) { // If it is average light...
50         Serial.println("It is average light!");
51         digitalWrite(4, HIGH); // turn left LED on
52         digitalWrite(2,LOW); // turn right LED off
53         s.write(0); // turn the motor 0 degrees
54     }
55     else { // If it's dark...
56         Serial.println("It is pretty dark!");
57         digitalWrite(4,HIGH); // Turn left LED on
58         digitalWrite(2,HIGH); // Turn right LED on
59         s.write(180); // turn the motor 180 degrees
60     }
61
62 // Ultrasonic sensor loop movement:
63 // generate 10-microsecond pulse to TRIG pin
64 digitalWrite(TRIG_PIN, HIGH);
65 delayMicroseconds(10);
66 digitalWrite(TRIG_PIN, LOW);
67
68 // measure duration of pulse from ECHO pin
69 duration_us = pulseIn(ECHO_PIN, HIGH);
70 // calculate the distance
71 distance_cm = 0.017 * duration_us;
72
73 if(distance_cm < DISTANCE_THRESHOLD)
74     s2.write(180); // rotate servo motor to 90 degree
75 else
76     s2.write(0); // rotate servo motor to 0 degree
77
78 // print the value to Serial Monitor
79 Serial.print("distance: ");
80 Serial.print(distance_cm);
81 Serial.println(" cm");
82
83 delay(1000); // don't spam the computer!
84 }

```

Arduino IDE code

The code mainly utilises IF/ELSE loops to allow for different motor outputs based on the distance and light readings.

There are two main IF/ELSE loops:

1. Light intensity input - servo motor 1 output and servo motor 2 output.
2. Distance input - servo motor 2 output.

Input: Light intensity and distance readings

Output:

LED 1 and 2 lighting based on light-intensity readings.

Servo motor 1 movement between 0° and 180 ° based on light intensity readings.

Servo motor 2 movement between 0° and 180 ° based on light intensity and distance readings.

Test 5 explicitly uses multiple inputs to generate a single output through servo motor 2 and also provides quantitative readings for further analysis of both inputs through the digital serial monitor on the Arduino IDE platform.

Conclusion:

The test successfully produced a single motor output from multiple dynamic inputs. The next step is to use the servo motor 2 movement to create a visual.

11.4E ARDUINO TEST 5: MOTOR CONNECTIONS

To create a smooth visual through the continuous motor movement, strings dipped in black paint were attached to the servo motor and with motor movement, they created different patterns on a white paper. Three iterations of string-attachments were tested:

1. [Attachment A]: **Two strings, 6 cm span**
2. [Attachment B]: **Two strings, 10 cm span**
3. [Attachment C]: **Single string**

The tests created interesting visuals on a 2D space, in response to changing light intensity and varying object distances from the set-up.

Control variables:

- Pattern of changing light intensity.
- Distances of each object against the ultrasonic sensor.
- Set-up height

Independent variable: Motor attachments

Dependent variable: 2D data visualisation

Arduino Set-up Elevation with Attachments [A], [B] and [C].

[Combined Output Video]

Attachment A: 6 cm span

[Process Video Link]

Attachment B: 10 cm span

[Process Video Link]

Attachment C: Single string

[Process Video Link]